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<p><i>Due to project-level deliverable submission deadlines, the information in this document is updated as of M36 (October 31, 2025). However, the authors intend to also publish the updates to the activities as soon as they are available. This will ensure that the most up-to-</i></p>	

date and comprehensive information is made available, supporting continuous improvement and strategic alignment across the cluster.

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List of acronyms

H²IOSC	Humanities and Heritage Open Science Cloud
RI	Research Infrastructure
CLARIN-IT	CLARIN Italian node (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure)
DARIAH-IT	DARIAH Italian node (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities)
E-RIHS	E-RIHS Italian node (European Heritage Science Research Infrastructure)
OPERAS	OPERAS Italian node (Open scholarly communication in the European research area for social sciences and humanities)
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSHOC	Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
ERIC	European Research Infrastructures Consortium
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
WP	Work Package
DHeLO	Digital Heritage Landscaping PlatfOrm
ERA	European Research Area
PiD	Persistent Identifier
GIS	Geographic Information System
CC BY NC	Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial

OJS	Open Journal System
DPH	Digital Philology Hub
FG	Focus Group
VLO	Virtual Language Observatory
BiDiAr	Bibliography of Digital Archaeology
TEI	Text Encoding Initiative
CIDOC CRM	International Committee for Documentation Conceptual Reference Model
DCMI	Dublin Core Metadata Initiative
LOD	Linked Open Data
FOAF	Friend Of A Friend
DA	Digital Archaeology
CH	Cultural Heritage
HS	Heritage Science

List of Figures

Some figures and illustrations in this deliverable retain their original Italian captions, as they are directly taken from internal documentation, pilot materials, or project outputs produced in their original linguistic context. The choice to preserve the original language aims to maintain consistency with the source data and the integrity of the visual materials.

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Executive Summary

This deliverable constitutes the second report on the Landscaping and Building Communities activities (WP2) within the Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) project, which brings together the Italian nodes of four ESFRI Research Infrastructures—CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS. The main aim of WP2 is to establish replicable methods for mapping and presenting the landscape of the scholarly communities of reference of the four RIs that make up the H2IOSC federation, and to gather insights necessary to support its development, integration, and sustainability.

The work package adopted a mixed-methods approach to conduct a comprehensive mapping of the national research landscape in the domains of Humanities, Linguistics, and Heritage Science. Key instruments included:

- a questionnaire-based survey, designed and disseminated across diverse disciplinary communities;
- focus groups, engaging junior and senior researchers to capture expectations and perceived gaps;
- semi-structured interviews, to gain deeper insights into practices and needs;
- discovery activities, both internal and external, to identify relevant datasets, tools, projects, protocols, and standards.

The findings provide a community-driven overview of existing resources, tools, and services, their degree of FAIR compliance, community practices, training needs, and give hints of important gaps. This evidence informs the project's broader objectives by providing key input for:

- resource integration and FAIRification (WP3),
- service design and deployment (WP6),
- pilot project development and innovation (WP7),
- synergies with the H2IOSC Marketplace (WP5),
- identifying training needs for targeted capacity-building (WP8), and
- reinforcing stakeholder engagement.

In addition to these community-mapping activities, WP2 developed a comprehensive Mapping and Landscaping Strategy, aimed at structuring and harmonising the documentation of resources, datasets, and tools across the participating infrastructures.

An output of WP2 is the DHeLO (Digital Humanities Landscaping PlatfOrm), which serves both as a demonstrator and a data environment where the outcomes of the mapping and landscaping activities are concretely implemented.

The main outcomes of WP2 populate the H2IOSC Permanent Observatory, a dynamic, continuously updated platform conceived within this WP and developed in synergy with the H2IOSC Marketplace. The Observatory acts as a long-term monitoring and intelligence tool, designed to collect, visualise, and analyse data on resources, tools, and user engagement.

The results of WP2 represent the first nation-wide, cross-infrastructure effort of this scale in Italy. By combining methodological rigor with active community involvement, WP2 not only delivers essential input for the technical and strategic WPs of H2IOSC, but also strengthens Italy's contribution to the European Open Science Cloud, reinforcing the alignment of national infrastructures with EOSC and ESFRI priorities.

The deliverable is structured into nine sections, each reflecting a distinct component of the WP2 activities and outcomes. Section 1 introduces the H2IOSC project and the objectives of WP2, describing its coordinating role in community engagement and landscape analysis across the Italian nodes of CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS. Section 2 illustrates the mixed-methods approach adopted to map research communities and infrastructures, integrating quantitative and qualitative methodologies through surveys, interviews, focus groups, and discovery activities. Sections 3 on questionnaire, 4 on interviews, and 5 on focus groups provide a detailed account of these activities, presenting the main findings practices, FAIRness compliance, community expectations and training needs emerging from questionnaires and participatory sessions. Section 6 defines the H2IOSC Mapping and Landscape Strategy, outlining the unified criteria, tools, and metadata schema developed to harmonise documentation practices across Ris. Section 7 introduces DHeLO (Digital Heritage Landscaping Platform) as a demonstrator that operationalises these results. Section 8 describes the conception, architecture, and development of the H2IOSC Observatory, the long-term monitoring environment designed to analyse and visualise data, tools, and user interactions in synergy with the H2IOSC Marketplace. Section 9 provides a synthesis of the main outcomes and perspectives of WP2, highlighting how the combination of landscape analysis and community building activities contributes to establishing a sustainable framework for the integration of Humanities and Cultural Heritage research within H2IOSC.

1. Introduction: the H2IOSC project and WP2

The H2IOSC project foresees the collaboration of four Italian nodes of CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS aiming at creating the Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud – H²IOSC: an Italian Cloud Network for research in humanities, linguistics, and heritage science. The project is structured into eight interconnected work packages, each addressing distinct aspects. This work package focuses on the establishment of mapping and monitoring strategies for assessing the national and international operation contexts for the four RIs, the characteristics of their user communities, and the specific data products they need and produce.

Figure 1: Map of the H²IOSC Cloud Network organization

1.1 Landscape and Building Communities

Work Package WP2, dedicated to Landscaping and Building Communities, aimed to map and assess the research landscape of the Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) cluster, operating within the broader framework of the European Research Area (ERA), EOSC, and ESFRI. As Research infrastructures (RIs) are increasingly recognized as strategic instruments to support innovation, interdisciplinarity, and openness in scholarly practices, it is important they keep track of the production and needs of their reference research communities. The H2IOSC initiative, aligned with EOSC principles, seeks to foster access to interoperable data, tools, and services in Digital Humanities, Linguistics, and Heritage Science, reinforcing the capacity of Italian RIs to respond to evolving research demands.

In this context, landscaping activities were conceived as structured efforts to map and document existing data resources, tools, services, community practices, and user needs across disciplines. These activities serve both infrastructure providers and scholarly users by enabling a continuous assessment of the ecosystem, identifying gaps, and informing future development trajectories. Landscaping is therefore understood not only as a preparatory

phase for onboarding resources into national repositories and marketplaces, but as a long-term strategy for infrastructural adaptation and sustainability.

WP2 was designed to produce an integrated overview of the current state of the art in the domains covered by the H2IOSC cluster. Its primary objective was to devise and put in place instruments to allow:

- Identifying and assessing resources relevant to participating communities;
- Evaluating the FAIRness and digitization status of such resources to prepare for their integration (WP3);
- Mapping standards and best practices, to be further supported via training activities (WP8);
- Identifying user needs regarding storage, processing, and software solutions (input to WP3 and WP6);
- Highlighting missing tools and services to inform innovation pilots (WP7);
- Engaging with stakeholders including relevant communities, public actors, and national projects;
- Prioritizing assets for inclusion in the National Cloud and H2IOSC marketplace.

To achieve these goals, the WP adopted a mixed-methods approach combining qualitative and quantitative instruments. These included a web-based questionnaire and structured interviews, focus groups, and both manual and semi-automated scouting protocols—termed *internal* and *external landscaping*—to identify and evaluate data resources, software tools, models, protocols, and projects. A notable result of this process is the establishment of the H2IOSC Observatory, designed as a replicable and dynamic framework for landscape monitoring and infrastructure planning.

The work was coordinated across all four participating RIs, each contributing both domain-specific expertise and methodological leadership. The WP was structured around shared activities, with each RI leading distinct tasks but engaging collaboratively:

- CLARIN-IT led the development of the overall methodology (§2), the structure of the questionnaire (§3), the other community involvement activities (§4.2, regarding the CLARIN Cafés), and the concept of the H2IOSC Observatory (§8).
- OPERAS-IT focused on the implementation of focus groups (§5) and the analysis of open publishing ecosystems.
- DARIAH-IT conducted comprehensive domain-specific inventories in Digital Humanities (§6).
- E-RIHS.it developed the DHeLO Platform (§7) and led interview-based data collection.

This collaborative structure enabled the integration of disciplinary perspectives and ensured a unified methodological basis across the diverse scholarly fields represented.

The WP established instruments that can support not only a one-time assessment, but a continuous and participatory model for continuous landscape monitoring. By involving scholarly communities in the collection and validation of evidence, WP2 promotes the co-construction of the infrastructures it surveys. This aligns with European efforts such as the ESFRI Landscape Analysis and the EOSC Observatory, while offering greater transparency and methodological replicability.

1.2 Synergies with other project's activities

Work Package 2 (WP2) established the analytical and informational foundations serving the activities set out in the other WPs. Through an extensive landscape analysis of the Humanities, Linguistics, and Cultural Heritage domains in Italy, WP2 generates essential baseline knowledge—identification of relevant resources (data, tools, methods, protocols, etc.) user needs, best practices, and FAIRness and interoperability statuses. These outcomes directly inform and support the activities defined and set up within the other Work Packages across the project, extending beyond the project's timeframe, as part of a continuous assessment cycle aligned with the long-term, ten-year maintenance and sustainability horizon.

Figure 2. Synergies with other WPs

The results of the landscaping activities (WP2) serve the fairification activities to carry out the technical integration of resources into the national research infrastructure, ensuring alignment with existing practices and FAIR principles (WP3). The identification of user needs – about data storage, processing, software tools, training and information-- further contributes to the planning and implementation of useful services within WP3 and WP6, and of training activities and materials in WP8. Additionally, by highlighting critical gaps and missing components in the current digital ecosystem, WP2 also informs and guides the design and development of pilot actions towards the development of innovative services in WP7. Moreover, the stakeholder mapping and prioritisation of resources and tools for cloud integration provide strategic inputs for planning the Marketplace offerings (WP5). Finally, the

H2IOSC Observatory is expected to be delivered to the community as a companion to the Marketplace. Additionally, both platforms developed by E-RIHS during the implementation of WP2—DHeLO and BiDiAr (see §7)—have served as key data sources for the Open Digital Archaeology HUB - ArchaeoHub— developed as a pilot within WP7 (<https://open-archaeohub.cnr.it>). Metadata on research projects, datasets, and interactive resources were retrieved from DHeLO via APIs, while bibliographic metadata was harvested from the BiDiAr Zotero library.

2. Overall Methodology

The approach is conceived to be cyclically repeatable over time, serving both as a sort of health check of the four infrastructures and as a strategic compass to monitor developments, detect emerging needs, and inform future directions.

A key feature of this work was the complexity derived from the diverse nature of the four Research Infrastructures (RIs) involved in the project (CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RIHS, and OPERAS), each operating within distinct disciplinary fields and engages with different types of data. In fact, despite operating under the broader umbrella of Humanities and Cultural Heritage, each infrastructure prioritizes a different set of practices, services, and research communities. CLARIN places emphasis on the development and dissemination of high-quality linguistic resources that are technically robust, well-documented, and interoperable, supporting researchers in fields such as linguistics, literature, history, sociology, and other language-related disciplines. DARIAH, is oriented toward the wider digital humanities landscape, with particular attention to areas including philology, lexicography, archival science, Latin and Romance languages, and art history. E-RIHS operates primarily in the cultural heritage domain, offering a range of repositories, services, and tools designed for the management, sharing, and preservation of heritage data, and promoting standards and best practices across the field. Finally, OPERAS focuses on advancing Open Science within the Humanities, emphasizing FAIR principles and supporting scholarly communication through platforms, tools, and services tailored to the needs of humanities researchers.

In the table below (Table 1) a brief description of each participating RI is provided, according to Part 3 of the ESFRI Roadmap 2021¹:

RI Name	ESFRI Roadmap Description
CLARIN	The Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure (CLARIN) is a distributed Research Infrastructure that provides easy and sustainable access for scholars in the Humanities and Social Sciences to FAIR digital language data – in written, spoken or multimodal form – and advanced tools to discover, explore, exploit, annotate, analyse or combine them, independent of their location. CLARIN is building a networked federation of language data repositories, service centres and centres of expertise, with single sign-on access for all members of the academic community in all participating countries. Tools and data from different centres are interoperable, so that data collections can be combined and tools from different sources can be chained to perform complex operations to support researchers in their work. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2016, CLARIN became a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2012. Since then several countries have joined either as full Member, or as Observer. The ultimate goal is to include all European countries as well as any interested third countries in or outside Europe. The majority of operations, services and centres of the CLARIN infrastructure is provided and funded by CLARIN Members (and Observers). They set up a national consortium, typically consisting of universities, research

¹ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/projects-and-landmarks/>

	institutions, libraries and public archives, of which at least one has the status of CLARIN Centre which is expected to create and provide access to digital language data collections, and digital tools and expertise for researchers to work with them.
DARIAH	The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) is a distributed Research Infrastructure to enhance and support digitally enabled research and teaching for Arts and Humanities. DARIAH is a network of people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an Infrastructure that sustains researchers in building, analysing and interpreting digital resources. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level. It preserves, provides access to and disseminates research that stems from these collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2006, DARIAH was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2014. DARIAH was awarded Landmark Status in 2016 as a Research Infrastructure that reached its Implementation Phase and was considered a pan-European hub of scientific excellence. Currently, DARIAH has 20 Members, one Observer and several Cooperating Partners in six non-member countries. Structurally, DARIAH operates through the Europe-wide networks of the Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs) and their constituent Working Groups. Each of the four VCCs is cross-disciplinary, multi-institutional, international and centred on a specific area of expertise. Within this structure, DARIAH has over 20 dynamic Working Groups to integrate national services under specific operational categories.
E-RIHS	The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) is a distributed Research Infrastructure to support research on heritage interpretation, preservation, documentation and management. E-RIHS delivers integrated access to expertise, data and technologies through a standardized approach, and integrate world-leading European facilities into an organization with a clear identity and a strong cohesive role within the global heritage science community. Through interdisciplinary access to the four platforms – E-RIHS ARCHLAB, E-RIHS DIGILAB, E-RIHS FIXLAB, E-RIHS MOLAB – E-RIHS supports a wide variety of research, from smaller object-focused case studies to largescale and longer-term collaborative projects, and stimulates innovation in instrumentation, portable technologies and data science. The long--term tradition of this field of research, the ability to combine science with innovation, and the support provided by EU-funded projects and integrating activities such as EUARTECH, CHARISMA, IPERION CH and IPERION HS in conservation science, and ARIADNE in archaeology, represent the background of E-RIHS. Entered in the ESFRI Roadmap 2016, E-RIHS was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in 2025. It offers access to a wide range of fixed and mobile instruments in national facilities of recognized excellence, physically accessible collections/archives

	and virtually accessible heritage repositories for standardized data storage, analysis and interpretation.
OPERAS	The Open Scholarly Communication in the European Research Area for Social Sciences and Humanities (OPERAS) is a distributed RI to enable Open Science and upgrade scholarly communication practices in the Social Sciences and Humanities in line with the EOSC. OPERAS pools resources and offers services to enable all SSH stakeholders to streamline their activities and maximize the societal impact, in an interdisciplinary, mission-driven approach. OPERAS fosters the co-creation and adoption of scholarly communication services addressing research needs in terms of discovery, content creation, quality assurance, dissemination, outreach, and evaluation of outputs. It catalyses knowledge and know-how sharing, practices adoption, and increases return on socio-economic investments. The OPERAS Concept and Design Phase dates back to 2012- 2018 when the coordinated actions to establish the network and shaping the project began. This effort led to the recognition of OPERAS as a project addressing High strategic potential area for research in SCI in the ESFRI Roadmap 2018. OPERAS started its Preparation Phase in 2019 by developing the business plan and governance model and promoting services creation and alignment for EOSC catalogue and transnational access. In 2019, OPERAS established the status of International non-profit Association under Belgian law (AISBL). Entered the ESFRI Roadmap 2021, OPERAS is striving to efficiently guarantee an efficient move to the Operation Phase with a coherent approach to technical, administrative, and financial issues and the establishment of OPERAS ERIC.

Table 1: Targeted Research Infrastructures

To address the complexity of the research landscape and the diversity of the communities involved, a Mixed Methods approach is adopted (Figure 2). This combines qualitative and quantitative strategies to:

- Provide a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of resources, tools and services, along with the needs expressed by the research communities
- Support related activities within the H²IOSC federation, particularly those focused on infrastructure construction and enhancement, service integration, user engagement, and training
- Allow for data-driven analysis and forecasting of user needs
- Elaborate a long-term strategy for the implementation and development of the H2IOSC Observatory.

Figure 3: Schema illustrating the Mixed Methods approach employed in the H2IOSC surveying activity.

Since the design of an apparatus capable of accounting for the existing projects, resources, tools, communities, best practices, and standards, in relation to each RI community involved in the project, requires the elaboration of a composite strategy, four primary instruments have been put together to collect structured information:

1. an online questionnaire-based survey designed to engage the stakeholder communities at large, and used to collect data on the use, production, and awareness of digital resources, tools, and Open Science practices, as well as training needs and alignment with FAIR principles;
2. focus group meetings, intended to complement quantitative data, are conducted with selected representatives of the target communities, including students, researchers, senior scholars and experts pertaining to the different disciplinary areas represented by the RIs. These sessions gather new insights on expectations, perceived gaps, and specific needs of the target communities in the use of digital infrastructures. Focus groups also foster interest in the project's activities. Participants are selected to ensure disciplinary and career-stage diversity across the four RIs;
3. a mapping matrix used to catalogue systematize data retrieved from the different sources on projects, datasets, tools, protocols and standards, across different disciplines;
4. a database for storing and facilitating navigation of all the collected data. It facilitates longitudinal analysis and supports the development of dashboards and observatory functions. Strategic starting points for this activity are existing repositories and

catalogues pertaining to two RIs involved in this project, which served as valuable initial sources of information (e.g. ILC4CLARIN).

Quantitative data (obtained primarily from the questionnaires and integrated with data derived from interviews and focus groups) is analysed using descriptive statistics to identify usage patterns, levels of awareness, and potential gaps. Qualitative data from focus groups is, on the other hand, thematically coded to extract recurrent concerns, needs, and suggestions. As a result, the triangulation of methods ensures robustness and consistency between findings and strategic recommendations.

The obtained insights are expected to address several key areas:

- **Prioritization:** identifying the most critical data resources, tools, and services that require urgent integration into the RIs and the H²IOSC Marketplace;
- **Enhancements, FAIRification, and servification:** determining which resources need improvement, FAIRification, or transformation into services;
- **Gaps identification:** detecting the absence of crucial resources, tools, and services within existing RIs, and addressing the specific needs of the Italian research communities;
- **Training needs:** identifying gaps in knowledge, skills, and competencies within the community to guide the development of targeted training programs, materials, and initiatives.

3. Questionnaire-based Survey

In this section we dig into the main landscaping activity carried out in the WP, the questionnaire-based survey.

3.1 Survey Methodology

Among the core surveying activity there is a designed and comprehensive online questionnaire aimed at directly engaging with the target research communities to gather essential information on key aspects, including the usage and needs related to data resources and technologies, awareness and current utilization of existing research infrastructure services, desiderata for new services or offerings, and training needs as perceived by community members (students, researchers, and experts pertaining to the different disciplinary areas represented by the Ris) . The latter focused particularly on competencies and skills identified throughout the survey, which are crucial for the development of effective training programs, materials, and campaigns.

The decision to create a single questionnaire applicable across all RI communities was initially made to prevent data fragmentation and mitigate the risk of "community overload" [**Error! Reference source not found.**], given the interdisciplinary nature of many researchers' fields of specialization, which can often span multiple RIs. The elaboration process began with identifying the expected information to be collected [**Error! Reference source not found.**], which encompassed several outcomes: the identification of stakeholders, user needs, training needs, priorities, gaps in available tools and services, existing resources both within and outside the RIs, the degree of FAIR compliance, the digitization of new resources, and best practices and standards.

A series of targeted questions were then formulated to acquire the necessary information for each of these objectives. For instance, to determine if a resource indicated by a respondent was FAIR-compliant, four additional questions were included to gather details on its location, cataloguing, persistent identifier (PID), and licensing. Each question was accompanied by explanatory notes to provide further clarification and to minimize potential misunderstandings. Additionally, definitions and references for potentially ambiguous acronyms or technical terms, such as FAIR and PID, were included to help participants understand the questions and respond accurately. This supplementary information also aimed to spark curiosity and encourage engagement. Each question was carefully designed and assigned a specific response format, including open-ended, single-choice, and multiple-choice options.

The questionnaire was assembled using LimeSurvey (Annex 1) and was structured into the following sections:

1. Personal Information & Privacy Policy: was aimed at collecting general information about the respondents age, career level, ERC research field, and institutional affiliation. Respondents were provided with a written informed consent form at the beginning of the questionnaire, before answering any questions, ensuring that they were fully aware of the purpose and scope of the data collection. All personal data collected follow the requirements of Article 13 of Regulation EU 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation), and responses have been analyzed and stored in anonymized and aggregated form.

2. Data Resources, Software, Tools, and Technologies: served to gather information about existing or newly created data resources, tools, etc. The goals here were multiple, from acquiring information on the state-of-the-art material within the Italian panorama, users' knowledge, expectations, and needs, as well as identifying gaps that should be addressed by other project's activities (e.g., points 3 and 7 in this list).
3. Projects: focused on collecting information on projects that have developed or are currently developing data resources, digital tools, software, or other technologies relevant to the respondents' disciplines, such as linguistics, archaeology, and philology.
4. Training needs: aimed at collecting respondents' expectations and comments regarding their personal training needs, with a particular focus on competencies and skills they deemed essential for future professional development.
5. Prior knowledge of RIs: was included to assess respondents' awareness of and level of engagement with the partnering RIs, which was considered critical for designing outreach and training actions to increase participation and engagement.
6. Publications: was aimed to explore how respondents and their institutions publish scientific articles. Questions focused on publication practices, awareness of institutional policies, and the extent of commitment to open-access publishing.
7. Contacts: e-mail addresses were collected at the end of the survey for contact purposes only and only after the respondents' informed consent.
8. Feedback: to share impressions and suggestions to the questionnaire and provide insights on how they learned about the survey.

Regarding the deployment of the questionnaire, a first draft was initially distributed to a selected group of colleagues representing various subcommunities of interest for the investigation; these colleagues acted as a test group and provided valuable first-hand feedback. Following this preliminary phase, the revised first official version of the questionnaire was forwarded to a control group composed of members from key Linguistics, Digital Humanities, and Cultural Heritage associations, for which the exact numerosity was known. This step allowed for an estimation of the potential participation of the broader community in the subsequent stages of the investigation. As a result of incorporating all the important feedback acquired from the first communities involved, we produced a second version of the questionnaire² that was divided in two parts: the first comprising the set of questions regarding the profile of respondents, training needs, knowledge of the RIs and publications, while the second part³ was dedicated to the description of resources, tools and services ever used and created by respondents. The final version of the questionnaire was widely disseminated across all target community members, associations, and mailing lists through various channels, including social networks, project and RI websites, conference presentations, and other outreach events (for details see D2.1 and Annex 1).

² The questionnaire-based survey is available at <https://survey.cnr.it/index.php?r=survey/index&sid=825638&lang=it>

³ To complete this second part of the questionnaire, respondents were asked at the end of the first part to indicate their preference for providing information either via a second online questionnaire or through a guided interview.

3.2 Results and analysis

The analysis conducted on the two versions of the questionnaire provided valuable insights into the participation, awareness, and use of Research Infrastructures (RIs), as well as the respondents' training needs and publication habits.

- Participation: overall, the first version of the questionnaire recorded 396 views with a completion rate of 22% (86 responses), while the second version had a higher relative participation, with 65% (97 responses) of participants completing the first part and 56% (29 responses) completing the second. The responses primarily came from researchers affiliated with the National Research Council (CNR), with 106 respondents, and universities, with 70 respondents.

Figure 4: summary of provenance of respondents

Figure 5: institutions of provenance of respondents

- Career and disciplinary field: the distribution of respondents by career level shows a higher presence of senior researchers, with 99 participants, followed by 44 mid-career researchers, 17 early-stage researchers, and 14 students. Most respondents belong to diverse disciplinary fields, with a predominance in the social sciences and humanities, particularly in fields such as SH4_9 (theoretical and computational linguistics), SH5_8 (cultural studies, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage), and SH6_3 (archaeology of early literate societies and early civilizations).

Figure 6: career level of respondents

Figure 7: disciplinary fields of respondents

- Use and creation of resources and tools: relational databases are the most frequently used, with 66 responses, followed by linguistic databases and written language corpora, both with 54 responses. GIS resources and geographic datasets are used by 49 participants, while the creation of new resources is most common in relational databases, with 56 responses, followed by written language corpora with 36 responses, and linguistic databases with 28. Less frequently used technologies include artificial intelligence applications and 3D/BIM modeling. Seventy-nine percent of respondents reported being aware of research infrastructures, with CLARIN, DARIAH, and E-RIHS being the most well-known, with 84, 100, and 104 responses, respectively. However, 20% of participants are unfamiliar with the available resources, while 73% of those who do not currently use them express an interest in exploring them further. Regarding the sharing of research data, 109 respondents expressed their willingness to deposit their materials, while 22 have already done so. The reasons cited by those who have not yet deposited data include the perception of outdated platforms,

complexities in managing data ownership, and the need for more information on sharing procedures.

Figure 8: summary of resources, tools and services mostly used by respondents

Figure 9: summary of resources, tools and services created by respondents

- Awareness and involvement with H2IOSC and Research Infrastructures: awareness of the existence of the H²IOSC federation stands at 53%, with 51 respondents aware of the initiative and 37 actively involved. However, 13 individuals involved are not sufficiently familiar with it, highlighting possible gaps in information dissemination. The identified training needs show a strong interest in access to archives and repositories, indicated by 112 responses, data analysis tools, with 104 preferences, and data management and preservation, with 80 responses. The preferred training methods are self-paced distance learning, chosen by 109 participants, followed by live online sessions, with 87 preferences. In-person sessions were selected by 36 participants, while the hybrid mode received 40 preferences. Regarding the sharing of training materials, 89 respondents expressed their willingness to share, while only 6 were opposed.

Figure 10: knowledge on the existence and characteristics of RIs by respondents

Figure 11: professional profiles of respondents unaware of the existence and characteristics of RIs

Figure 12: list of Ris known by respondents

Figure 13: respondents use and consultation of Ris services

Figure 14: respondents' future expectations on RIs

Figure 15: respondent's interest and availability in depositing their data and research results in Ris repositories

Figure 16: respondents' awareness of the H²IOSC project

Figure 17: respondents' involvements in the H²IOSC project

- Publication practices: the most widely used system is OJS, with 87 responses, followed by WordPress, used by 24 participants, and Drupal, selected by 5 participants. The most common type of open-access publications includes scientific journals, with 141 responses, followed by conference proceedings with 75 and datasets with 42. Creative Commons licenses are the most frequently adopted, with CC BY used by 38

respondents and CC BY-NC by 29, while 44% of respondents do not use any specific license. Finally, the follow-up of the questionnaires recorded a high level of interest, with 59 respondents wanting to be contacted again and 52 ready to participate in further questionnaires. Additionally, 14 participants have expressed their availability for in-depth interviews, highlighting a significant willingness to collaborate and further explore the topics addressed.

Figure 18: respondents' publication practices

Figure 19: respondents' types of publications in Open Access

Figure 20: most common licenses used by respondents

4. Interviews and other community-involving activities

To complement the results of the questionnaire and gain a more detailed understanding of community needs, a series of semi-structured interviews was conducted with a selection of researchers operating within the SH6, SH5 and SH4 disciplinary sectors. The aim was to explore in greater depth how members of the scholarly community relate to digital data — in terms of usage, creation and dissemination — and to investigate their expectations, needs, concerns, and habits regarding data management and sharing practices.

As part of the broader strategy for landscape assessment in the H2IOSC project, each infrastructure has curated a series of community-facing initiatives to gather expert feedback, foster dialogue, and align research infrastructure services with the needs and practices of scholarly communities.

4.1. Structure of interviews and results

The structure of the interviews generally followed this outline:

- Research field
 - Briefly define your primary and secondary research areas using keywords.
- Use of digital tools in research
 - Use of already digital data
 - How frequently do you use data that is already digital (excluding bibliographic data)?
 - What types of data do you most often search for?
 - Do you consider that research infrastructures—such as data aggregators—offer added value to your research or that of your collaborators?
- Digitisation of data
 - How frequently do you use tools for digitizing data?
 - In both cases, do you tend to rely on systems you're already familiar with, or do you explore new resources to obtain data?
- Processing of digital data
 - Do you process data using digital or analogue methods?
 - What categories of software do you use most frequently?
 - What digital tools do you consider essential for the advancement of your discipline?
- Availability of digital tools
 - In your current research context, do you feel that the available tools meet your needs?
 - Is there anything important that is missing or particularly difficult to use?
 - Would you be willing to pay for a service that fills these gaps?
- Data production and management
 - Do you or your team produce digital data in the course of your research?
 - When selecting software tools to invest in (for yourself or your research group), how important is it that they are open source?
 - If the results were the same, would you prefer open source tools?

- If the results were different, would you prioritize output quality or methodological openness and data shareability?
- Data sharing and dissemination
 - How important is sharing and publishing your data outside of traditional publication formats?
 - In what ways would you like your research data to be made accessible?

Due to the informal nature of the interviews and the lack of consent from participants for both audio recording and name disclosure, it was not possible to produce full transcripts or attribute statements to specific individuals. Instead, structured notes were taken during each conversation. This respect for privacy created a more open and relaxed atmosphere, allowing participants to speak freely and raise critical points. The insights gathered in this way have been analysed and synthesised in the results section⁴.

The sample, although limited in size, comprised 27 individuals selected to reflect a range of professional experiences and academic profiles. Due to privacy agreement, it was decided to maintain the identity of the participant anonymous; nevertheless, we would like to deeply thank all the individuals who generously agreed to be interviewed and shared their experiences and reflections. Particular attention was given to ensuring a balance across different career stages, following the same logic adopted for the questionnaire. The distribution of respondents can be defined as follows (Table 2):

Definition	Number	Role
Students	7	Master & Phd Students
Early-career researchers	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● University researchers ● Postdoctoral fellows (<i>assegnisti di ricerca</i>) ● Fixed-term researchers (CNR & University) ● CNR Researchers – Level III
Mid-Career researchers	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CNR Researchers – Level I ● Associate Professors (University) ● Ministry officials
Senior Researchers	7	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CNR Research Directors ● CNR Senior Research ● Full Professors (University)

Table 2: Distribution of interviews participants

While the relatively small size of the sample may limit the generalizability of the findings, efforts were made to ensure diversity and representativeness across career stages and institutional backgrounds. This exploratory phase was primarily intended to provide a qualitative foundation for identifying recurring issues and needs, rather than to produce statistically generalisable results.

⁴ Preliminary insights on the interviews were published in (Mancuso et al. 2025; Mancuso 2025).

The interviews provided a very complex, albeit partial, snapshot of the practices, perceptions, and challenges that characterise the relationship between the research community, especially in archaeology, and digital data. One of the clearest findings is the strong demand, expressed across all career levels, for more structured training across the field. This need was spontaneously mentioned by 14 participants, mainly in the early- and mid-career groups, and received unanimous agreement when addressed directly during the interviews. The type of training envisioned spans a wide range of topics, from data management to digital documentation. In two cases, interviewees explicitly invoked the need not just for a wider 'digital literacy', but for a broader data culture and critical awareness of the informational potential embedded in the data that the community itself produces. A second significant theme concerns the widespread and transversal engagement, at all levels, with both the production and the use of digital data, confirming what was already inferable by the questionnaire results itself. In terms of usage, participants frequently (88%) mentioned popular archaeological databases and online services (such as [Beazley Archive](#)) as well as well-known WebGIS (such as the [Geoportale Nazionale per l'Archeologia](#)). Types of data produced ranged from inventories and lists to relational databases, GIS systems, statistical datasets, 3D surveys and virtual reconstructions, and even interactive notebooks or specific software or plugins. However, a structural issue, already inferred but now clearly confirmed, also emerged: most of this work begins from scratch, without building on existing datasets or infrastructures. This isolated approach appears to correlate with a widespread lack of familiarity with metadata standards, which several interviewees (ca. 50%) identified as a priority area for targeted and conscious training, as well as for broader thematic aggregation strategies. Some interviewees (28%) also pointed out that infrastructures themselves could play a central role in this process, not only as providers of training, but as reference points for defining and actively disseminating best practices. This could happen, some suggested, through the creation of guidelines (12%) or through the provision of ready-to-use and customisable tools and services (16%) aligned with community needs and standards for data management.

Particularly telling is the variety of definitions attributed to the very concept of 'data'. Across the interviews, the term was used to refer to a wide range of materials: from basic lists of artefacts to raw excavation records, from remote sensing outputs to unprocessed 3D scans. This semantic ambiguity also informs attitudes towards sharing practices: many respondents equated open access publication of written outputs with the sharing of data. While this position is perfectly legitimate, it coexists with other, more data-centric views that emphasise the need to publish structured, reusable datasets as independent research products (16%). In few cases, there was even a clear resistance to the idea of sharing raw or unprocessed data (20%). One particularly thoughtful observation pointed out that relying mostly on raw data sharing is not always sustainable, given that datasets often represent significant investments of time, training and financial resources. At least 36% of the interviewees, primarily early- and

mid-career researchers, as well as some PhD students, raised concerns about the current lack of formal recognition for dataset publication in academic evaluation. Compared to the established value of journal articles or monographs based on the same data, datasets are still perceived as having little or no weight in career progression. This reinforces the central role of written publications, both in print and digital formats, which continue to be perceived and used as the primary vehicles for recognition and the preferred medium for communicating research outputs. In this respect, all interviewees acknowledged the importance of open access as a mode of scholarly dissemination. Nevertheless, in 15 cases, this support was accompanied by an awareness of the costs associated with open access publishing. In this context, digital data is often viewed as an interactive complement to a publication – a kind of navigable illustration – rather than as an autonomous object with its own life cycle, capable of being circulated, updated, or reinterpreted over time by other actors.

In summary, what emerges from this evaluation is the complex image of a field that is, on the one hand, remarkably innovative in its experimentation with digital data and its potential, but on the other, still deeply rooted in traditional scholarly formats of transmission. Digital technologies are widely present, used, and valued, but rarely experienced as a native or structuring dimension of collaborative research practice. At present, it seems that digital infrastructures tend to be perceived more as functional supports than as fully embedded ecosystems within everyday scholarly routines.

4.2 Other community-targeted activities: format and results

In line with the project's landscape assessment goals, CLARIN-IT and DARIAH-IT carried out dedicated actions to engage with scholarly communities, promote interaction, and ensure that services evolve in response to concrete research practices and needs.

The CLARIN community contributed through its series of monthly online “Cafés” — informal and interactive discussion sessions that bring together researchers, lecturers, students, infrastructure staff, and language resource experts to exchange ideas and address emerging topics in digital humanities and linguistic data infrastructures. Between November 2022 and May 2025, the CLARIN-IT team at ILC participated in and supported a wide range of CLARIN Cafés organised by CLARIN ERIC, each typically involving around 30 participants from academia and research institutions.

These sessions addressed a broad spectrum of subjects — from text and data mining exceptions, multilingual corpora, and digital tools for online learning, to copyright in AI-generated content, lexical semantic change, and pedagogical corpora containing sensitive language. More recent Cafés have expanded to cover translation technologies and workflows for SSH researchers, which attracted a broader interdisciplinary audience including translators, technical experts, and professionals working with multilingual data. Through its continued engagement, CLARIN-IT has contributed to knowledge exchange and

capacity building within the H2IOSC network, strengthening the link between the Italian and European research communities and ensuring that user feedback informs infrastructure development.

In each Café session, participants share experiences, highlight infrastructural gaps, propose workflows, and reflect on organisational and technical requirements. Through open dialogue and moderated exchange, the CLARIN Café served as a mechanism for bottom-up feedback into the infrastructure ecosystem.

These meetings addressed various challenges such as multilingual and annotated corpora, pedagogical resource creation, rights management in language data, automated transcription or annotation workflows, and user-driven infrastructure design. For example, the July 2024 Café entitled *“Of Users and Infrastructures”* explored how language researchers engage with resources and what infrastructures must provide in a post-pandemic digital research landscape.

DARIAH-IT launched its own (i) series of community-oriented events and (ii) co-design working sessions. Between December 2023 and June 2025, a total of 20 dedicated meetings were held, including five public seminars under the title *“I giovedì di H2IOSC”* and 15 working sessions devoted to the design and implementation of the Digital Philology Hub (DPH) pilot (Activity 7.3).

The *“giovedì di H2IOSC”* seminars served as a forum for targeted discussions on topics such as the lemmatization of ancient Italian, digital library models, AI-supported transcription workflows, and sustainability in digital research infrastructure. These events gathered feedback from scholars, technical experts, and institutional stakeholders, providing valuable insights into research practices, infrastructural needs, and methodological challenges. The feedback collected directly informed the mapping activity, helping to define key metadata fields such as data standards, technical readiness levels, and the role of responsible institutions. Moreover, these sessions helped surface community priorities for reusable workflows, openness, and technical interoperability.

Complementing this public dialogue, the DPH working sessions supported a structured co-design process aimed at shaping the DARIAH-IT Pilot. Held monthly, these meetings enabled continuous feedback loops between researchers and infrastructure providers. As a result, core requirements for the pilot were collaboratively defined. This iterative process ensured the alignment of pilot components with both scholarly workflows and infrastructure capabilities.

In the context of H2IOSC, the interplay between the CLARIN Cafés and the *“Giovedì di H2IOSC”* series broadens the scope of WP2’s landscape mapping activities. While the CLARIN Cafés emphasise language-resource infrastructures, multilingual issues, and cross-domain digital humanities practices, the *“Giovedì”* seminars focus on heritage sciences, digital philology, and

the Italian node ecosystem. Together, they create shared touchpoints between linguistic, heritage, and digital-humanities infrastructures, ensuring that service design, metadata documentation, and workflow development reflect diverse disciplinary needs.

Collectively, these engagement activities contribute to the overall community mapping strategy. They clarify the categories of resources to be identified—including not only software and services but also workflows, data types, and user support mechanisms—and validate key criteria such as usability, openness, standard compliance, and integration potential. Ultimately, the interviews and participatory events serve as both a diagnostic and developmental layer of landscape analysis, grounding the mapping methodology in real SSH research practices and community expectations. In Deliverable 1.3 “H2IOSC Training Activities Coordination and Management Procedures” a complete list of engagement and dissemination activities is provided for further information.

5. Focus Groups

5.1 Focus Group Methodology

Focus groups are a widely used research technique in the humanities and social sciences. They are used to collect rich data derived from verbal interactions among a group of people brought together specifically to discuss a particular topic, through a series of stimuli provided by a researcher (Caradonna et al., 2025).

A typical focus group (FG) involves 6–8 participants, a researcher who proposes discussion topics and moderates verbal interactions, and an assistant who follows the discussion and notes particularly relevant points and topics. Several variations of this basic setup exist: the number of participants can be increased to a maximum of 12–13, and the assistant can be replaced by a second researcher acting as a critical friend. This researcher assists the main moderator in managing interactions and covering the topics to ensure all knowledge objectives are achieved. The most common methodology involves FG meetings taking place in person in a suitably equipped room with furnishings that allow for easy interaction.

According to traditional methodology, the discussion takes place in a dedicated environment — usually a room equipped with audio-visual recording equipment — and lasts between one and a half and two hours. This phase is very important as the significance of the data is directly related to the discussion. The discussion depends on the stimuli provided, the researcher's ability to encourage communication and interaction between participants, and the characteristics of the participants invited.

Depending on the research problem and the questions to be answered, the focus group follows a standard procedure.

1. The characteristics that participants must meet are identified.
2. The interviewees are identified and invited to attend on a given day, at a given place and time.
3. The discussion takes place, which is normally audio-video recorded.
4. The discussion is transcribed.
5. The data from the discussions is analysed.

Of the above stages, the first and fourth (transcription of the discussion) are undoubtedly the most important. In the first case, it is crucial that the participants possess the necessary knowledge and experience; otherwise, they are unable to respond to the stimuli, and any silence or inappropriate responses could hinder or divert the discussion. In the second case, the transcription should retain as much non-verbal communication, 'fillers' and other forms of expression as possible, since, as communication theory tells us, explicit speech constitutes only part of a person's communicative message. Fillers, tone of voice, gestures, and all other forms of non-verbal communication (e.g. nodding or shaking one's head, gesturing with one's hands) are of great importance.

In the analysis of the data, it is important to look at all communications. From the very beginning and then including factors such as the group atmosphere. For example, a participant's statement could trigger a series of consents that are only manifested through non-verbal communication (gestures of assent, activation of the body through the posture of the torso, etc.) but do not produce verbal communication. If this involves all participants, it creates a climate of consensus, even if only momentary, on a statement, so much so that it can then be taken up in the data analysis as “the whole group agrees with what ... said”.

What has just been expressed represents the cognitive power that can be gained from a group meeting. Obviously, the difficulty lies in the fact that when presenting the results, it is necessary to provide specific interpretations, otherwise the impression could be given that the analysis does not perfectly match the data.

In recent decades, this classic approach has been complemented by group meetings held via videoconference using web applications.

Web-based technologies have made it possible to expand the opportunities for using the focus group technique, with obvious advantages for research activities such as those offered by WP2, for example.

In WP2, landscaping activities were carried out using a mixed method approach, i.e. surveys with quantitative and qualitative tools, and the focus groups planned as part of the project activities were conducted via video call.

This made it possible to involve a very large audience of participants, even though they were in different areas of the peninsula, thereby substantially reducing the costs of the activity.

Below, we describe the phase of defining the meetings.

The WP research group planned four focus groups, two of which were conducted between July and December 2024, and the remaining two in March 2025.

First, the characteristics decided during the planning phase are listed, followed by the characteristics of the participants who took part in the meetings.

5.2 Features of planned focus groups.

During the planning phase, it was decided that each group would consist of eight participants. The following variables were monitored for these participants: biological sex, age, membership of the four macro research areas to which the infrastructures confederated in H²IOSC belong, and orientation towards innovation (Tables 3 and 4).

Women

Men

Age	PhD students	Post-doctoral researchers/Junior research fellows	PhD students	Post-doctoral researchers/Junior research fellows	Total
25 - 28	2	2	2	2	8
29 - 32	2	2	2	2	8
Total	4	4	4	4	16

Table 3: Number and characteristics of the focus group JUNIOR 1 and 2

Women

Men

Age	researchers	Senior Researchers/University professors	Senior researchers	Researchers/University professors	Total
33 - 40	2	2	2	2	8
41 +	2	2	2	2	8
Total	4	4	4	4	16

Table 4: Number and characteristics of the focus group SENIOR 1 and 2

Suggestions for infrastructures regarding the identification of group participants regarding orientation towards innovation.

The identification of these figures was delegated to the four infrastructures.

It was asked to invite PhD students, post-doctoral researchers/junior research fellows and senior researchers/university professors that were:

- open and extroverted individuals who allow for free and open discussion of the possibilities for innovative and digital development in the SSH;
- open-minded scholars with a strong focus on the future;
- participants with solid approaches to both “classical” and “innovative” SSH studies;
- open and extroverted researchers who can discuss the possibilities for future development of the SSH but who are not ideologically biased or overly enthusiastic;
- Scholars who also express critical but constructive views on the digital future.

The four groups were named: FGSENIOR1, FGSENIOR2 and FGJUNIOR1, FGJUNIOR2.

From a theoretical standpoint (see Figure 1), the research team resolved to proceed with two distinct groups. The initial group (FGSENIOR1) comprised individuals who exhibited a marked propensity towards exploring novel avenues of research, utilizing innovative or experimental digital resources, and possessing substantial research experience. The second group (FGJUNIOR1) consisted of individuals who, despite possessing a high level of education, lacked extensive research experience. The former group was characterized by a strong focus on the

present of learning (FGJUNIOR1), coupled with a positive outlook towards the future, driven by a desire to pursue a research career (FGSENIOR1).

The research group adopted this theoretical position subsequent to the observation that the digital dimension exhibited a divergent geometry between the two groups. Senior researchers and professors belong to a generation (Generazione X)⁵ where the digital dimension has grown in importance, while doctoral students and junior researchers belong to a generation (Generazione Z)⁶ in which digital technology was already an integral part of both everyday life and study and research activities. This discrepancy, when considered in conjunction with the varying degrees of research experience, gives rise to disparate expectations regarding infrastructure orientation amongst users of differing ages.

Figure 21- Expected conceptual positioning of the two focus groups.

The participants of the four groups have been invited to deliberate on their expectations regarding the outcomes, future developments, and long-term sustainability of the project. Furthermore, researchers and students have been assigned the following tasks:

⁵ In sociology, Generation X is a term widely used in the Western world to describe the generation born in different years depending on the source (1964-1979 or 1965-1980) who lived through a crucial historical transition, marking the shift from the analogue to the digital age^[1].

The term was coined by Canadian writer Douglas Coupland, https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generazione_X

⁶ Generation Z (or Centennials, Digitalians, Gen Z, iGen, Plurals, Post-Millennials, Zoomers) is the generation of people born between the second half of the 1990s^{[1][2][3][4][5]} and the first half of the 2010s^{[6][7]} (although the exact numbers vary depending on the different definitions presented),^{[8][9][10][11]} and whose members are generally the children of Generation X (1965-1979) and the last baby boomers (1946-1964), https://it.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generazione_Z

- describe current research and teaching activities, especially those affiliated with the university.
- outline research and study activities from the last five years;
- discuss the pros and cons of research infrastructures, as well as the knowledge and practices of open science and FAIR data;
- talk about expectations for a research infrastructure dedicated to SSH, the type of access to a research infrastructure and willingness to provide training on how to use it.

5.3 Results and analysis

This section reports on the main findings and observations emerging from the WP2 focus groups. As is often the case in participatory research, some discrepancies arose between the planned methodology and the actual implementation, particularly regarding participants' availability and meeting schedules. Nonetheless, the focus groups produced rich qualitative evidence, shedding light on key aspects of user experience and engagement within the research infrastructure landscape.

As stated in the *methodology section*, four meetings were arranged: two with students and young researchers, and two with senior researchers and university professors.

These meetings were held online, with the calls being recorded and transcribed using Microsoft Teams.

The total number of participants included in the study was 24, comprising twelve males and twelve females, who attended two meetings (Figure 28).

Figure 22: Composition by biological sex of the four focus groups

Figure 23: Composition by study area of the four focus groups

Figure 29 illustrates the composition of the four groups in terms of field of study. Linguists were the researchers who participated in the greatest numbers, followed by philosophers, archaeologists, and then philologists.

The average age of the twelve respondents was 35.4 years, with the youngest participant being 25 and the oldest 61.

The focus groups had also the following objectives:

- To facilitate the involvement of communities belonging to the four confederating infrastructures;
- To corroborate the survey results with qualitative data;
- To gather qualitative data on the digital humanities experiences of the project's various audiences⁷.

The findings from the four meetings are intriguing; however, it is not feasible to provide a comprehensive overview of the results in this article. The analysis presented herein pertains, in a broad sense, to the utilization, perceptions and expectations that congregate or differentiate the four groups. Both in the groups held in 2024 and in the groups held in 2025, respondents were categorized into two additional groups: those who were acquainted with an infrastructure and had utilized it, and those who had merely been aware of it but had never employed it. Amongst those who had only been exposed to the concept of an infrastructure, a significant proportion expressed a sense of curiosity regarding the potential utilization of such a system in the future. In all meetings, great expectations were expressed about the study and research opportunities that a digital infrastructure should provide, with these expectations varying according to the field of study. For instance, the field of linguistics has

⁷ VERBI Software. (2021). MAXQDA 2022 [macOS Sonoma 14.4.1]. Berlin, Germany: VERBI Software. Available from maxqda.com.

advocated for a platform capable of encompassing all the resources, tools and services essential for the management of FAIR linguistic corpora to overcome the current difficulties encountered in their research. *“The major difficulty that I identify is the issue of interoperability and FAIR resources, meaning that they are open, searchable and, in simple terms, a tool that I in Padua, Giovanni in Basel and Luis in India can all use in the same way, in a sense, without having to translate every time because the metadata doesn't work, right?”* (LINGDDFJ1M participant in the FGJUNIOR1)

The necessity for the platform to demonstrate a high degree of flexibility was emphasized, with a view to facilitating the seamless integration of existing resources in novel ways. In contrast, archaeologists emphasized the significance of the platform as a repository for not only publications but also all "field" materials.

The common ground shared by researchers and students is their familiarity with the principles of open science and the FAIR guidelines, yet their perspectives diverge the practical implementation of these principles in research methodologies. A notable distinction emerges when it comes to the transfer of principles to research practice, a point that expert researchers underscore as a challenge. In contrast, archaeologists have raised numerous issues relating to the rights of excavation and use of materials, especially when research takes place on non-Italian territory.

The findings from the four meetings are intriguing; however, it is not feasible to provide a comprehensive overview of these in this article. The analysis presented herein pertains, in a general sense, to the applications, perceptions and expectations that coalesce or differentiate between the two groups.

Both in the groups held in 2024 and in the groups held in 2025, respondents were divided into two categories: those who had both heard of an infrastructure and used it, and those who had only heard of it but had never used it. Amongst those who had only been exposed to the concept of an infrastructure, a significant proportion expressed a sense of curiosity regarding the potential utilization of such a system in the future. It was asserted on both occasions that considerable expectations were in place regarding the study and research opportunities that a digital infrastructure should provide. It is evident that these expectations vary according to the field of study. For instance, the field of linguistics has advocated for a platform capable of encompassing all the resources, tools, and services essential for the management of linguistic corpora. Furthermore, emphasis was placed on the necessity for the platform to exhibit a high degree of flexibility, thereby facilitating the reuse of existing resources in innovative ways. In contrast, archaeologists emphasized the significance of the platform as a repository for not only publications but also all "field" materials.

It is evident that the experiences and opinions of researchers (FGSENIOR1, FGSENIOR2) and students and young researchers (FGJUNIOR1, FGJUNIOR2) are both unified and divided by the issues of open science and the FAIR principles. A commonality shared by the groups is the awareness of the FAIR principles. However, a divergence emerges when exploring the practical implementation of these principles in research endeavors. It is important to note

that leading researchers have underscored the intricacies and difficulties inherent in the process of transitioning from theoretical principles to concrete research practices. For instance, archaeologists have raised numerous issues relating to the rights of excavation and the use of materials, especially when research takes place on non-Italian territory. A growing body of evidence suggests that students and early-career researchers have demonstrated a notable degree of receptiveness to the tenets of Open Science and the FAIR principles.

"No, I agree with both LINGDDFJ1M and LINGESJ1F, that research must be open, because otherwise we cannot move forward." (ARCHFSJ1M participant in the FGJUNIOR1)

This tendency may be attributed to two primary factors. Firstly, these individuals have limited experience in research however, as we mentioned above, they are also representatives of "Generation Z", meaning they are "more digital", i.e. with a mindset that is more oriented towards sharing, teamwork and working directly with web-based tools and secondly, it appears that the projects with which they are engaged do not present any significant challenges or complexities. Nevertheless, this aspect prompts students to engage in introspection. In many cases, students have elevated expectations of their course and future. Indeed, one thing that students and young researchers are quite sure of, and they all agree on, and that is the fact that "(...) science is not science if it is not open (...)".

It is evident that the fieldwork has furnished elements that imply that the four groups are not considerably divergent in their conception of the digital future. The "delta" (see Figure 30) that remains between those with extensive research experience and those entering the field today is less pronounced than expected. Of greater significance are the observed differences and the enthusiastic and motivated approach to the different topics related to the use and production of resources, tools and services of digital infrastructures for SSH.

Figure 24: Positioning of the four focus groups obtained after the discussions.

The rationale for incorporating qualitative instruments such as Focus Group discussions is predicated on the premise that, in comparison with alternative methodological constructs that have been adopted to date, focus groups constitute a more flexible instrument about adaptability and reusability for subsequent follow-ups.

In accordance with the definition provided by Corbetta (Corbetta 2014, 15), the interviews conducted have facilitated the acquisition of an in-depth understanding by the landscaping team of the preferences of the stakeholders regarding resources, tools, and services related to all the communities involved in the project. Focus group meetings have facilitated the execution of the questionnaire format, while also allowing for additional comments, ideas, and suggestions, providing valuable food for thought for the Marketplace implementation and the empowerment of the national RIs nodes, as well as for the elaboration of a long-term sustainability strategy for the H²IOSC federation.

6. Landscape analysis of participating RIs

The landscaping activity carried out within WP2 aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of the current ecosystem of digital resources, services, and tools across the participating Research Infrastructures. Its purpose was to map existing assets, identify overlaps and complementarities, and detect potential gaps in the provision of services supporting Humanities and Cultural Heritage research.

This activity represents a crucial step toward achieving one of the project's main objectives: establishing a shared understanding of the heterogeneous landscape in which the four RIs operate. By analysing how each infrastructure addresses data management, interoperability, and user engagement, the landscaping process contributes to outlining the baseline upon which future harmonisation and integration actions can be developed within H2IOSC.

In this sense, the landscaping exercise not only serves as a descriptive effort but also as an analytical framework, enabling cross-infrastructure comparison and the identification of strategic areas for collaboration and FAIRification across the Humanities and Cultural Heritage domains.

To ensure a consistent and comparable approach across the four Research Infrastructures, the landscaping activity was developed within a common analytical framework based on a shared set of descriptors, including data typology, access conditions, interoperability features, and alignment with FAIR principles. Designing this unified mapping strategy required not only the standardisation of data collection procedures, but also careful consideration of the distinctive characteristics, priorities, and operational contexts of each RI. The resulting integrated representation of tools, datasets, and projects provides a comprehensive overview of domain-specific methodologies and technological frameworks, enabling an assessment of the current degree of convergence among infrastructures and highlighting areas where further harmonisation and technical integration can be effectively pursued in subsequent phases of the project.

6.1 RIs Landscape strategy

Each RI defined its own objectives for the landscaping activity, along with tailored approaches for collecting and organizing the necessary information. Beyond fulfilling individual goals, this joint effort provides an initial overview of the broader landscape, highlighting shared development priorities, areas for potential technological convergence, and gaps to be addressed in the integration of datasets, tools, and services. The work directly contributes to the objectives of WP2 by fostering alignment and synergy across RIs and laying the groundwork for effective FAIRification strategies, adapted to the specificities of different disciplinary domains and resource types.

To guide their respective contributions, CLARIN-IT (Monachini M. and Frontini F. , 2023), DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT established specific landscaping criteria based on their unique disciplinary focus, community requirements, and infrastructure mandates. These criteria were discussed collectively to ensure coherence and identify points of overlap or

complementarity. Tables 5, 6, and 7 present a comparative overview of the needs, priorities, and perspectives expressed by each RI as part of this coordinated strategy.

RI	CLARIN-IT
LANDSCAPING OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> strengthening of the infrastructure (general): enrich CLARIN resource catalogues; Identifying gaps in data and software resources, in order to guide actions for their onboarding and deposition into CLARIN-IT certified repositories mapping the needs of the target communities reaching out to resource stakeholders
LANDSCAPING CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Digital(ised) language resources related to language technology, linguistics, NLP or applications in the Digital Humanities resources produced or primarily used by domain experts/scholars Deposited in a CLARIN certified repository (F) clear license (A) format/standard (I) in/for the Italian language and/or classical and ancient indoeuropean languages (R)
LANDSCAPING SOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CLARIN VLO Sector-specific conferences and symposia: esp. AIUCD, CLIC-IT Interviews and dedicated events
LANDSCAPING TOOLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> spreadsheet for internal landscaping Search into conference proceedings H2IOSC Landscaping Questionnaire
RESOURCES INFORMATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> authors status (created/updated/used) publications related to the resource year of creation/integration reference project type of resource type of data (oral/written/video)

Table 5: CLARIN-IT Landscape criteria

RI	DARIAH-IT
LANDSCAPING OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> creation of a resource catalogue to be made available to other WPs evaluation of the FAIRness of the resources mapping the needs of the target communities identification of available resources/tools in relation to their domain and use; mapping of unmet needs in line with the previous objective

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> reaching out to resource stakeholders
LANDSCAPING CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> resources related to texts, literature, and the language of Old Italian resources produced or primarily used by domain experts resources involving DARIAH participation relevance to the objectives of the Pilots (WP7) resources related to the following academic-disciplinary sectors: L-FIL-LET/09, L-FIL-LET/10, L-FIL-LET/12, L-FIL-LET/13
LANDSCAPING SOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DARIAH Registry DARIAH Tools and Services Catalogue Opera del Vocabolario Italiano (OVI-CNR): http://www.ovi.cnr.it/Progetti.html SSHOC Marketplace Sector-specific conferences and symposia Recommendations from domain experts and partners Journal of Cultural Heritage Umanistica Digitale Digital Humanities Quarterly Annali d'Italianistica Digital Medievalist Digital Scholarship in the Humanities Humanist Studies and the Digital Age International Journal of Heritage in the Digital Era Studies in Digital Heritage Scientific reports and sector-specific articles on Zenodo (used as a repository for several DARIAH-affiliated projects)
LANDSCAPING TOOLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> spreadsheet for internal landscaping research in journals and other sources using keywords or thematic search consultation with domain experts and project partners collaborations with partners and other institutes
RESOURCES INFORMATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lead RI/Institute Description Current status Curator Link to the webpage and source code Standard/format

Table 6: DARIAH-IT Landscape criteria

RI	E-RIHS.it
LANDSCAPING OBJECTIVES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> survey of existing digital resources for Heritage Science (HS) and Cultural Heritage (CH)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • survey of the main services (tools) developed for / used by the research community • identification of the research community's needs • survey of the main research centers actively involved in creating digital resources for HS and CH • implementation of the dataspace
LANDSCAPING CRITERIA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • thematic relevance: digital datasets related to HS or CH • thematic relevance: tools developed by / used by the research community • thematic relevance: open access journals and their citation network over the last 5 years
LANDSCAPING SOURCES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IperionHS • ARIADNEplus • Europeana • Zenodo Communities • Dataspace ISPC • scientific articles and conference proceedings published in open access: <i>Archeologia e Calcolatori</i> journal repository • responses to the Landscaping questionnaire • scientific articles in open access journals: Scopus repository. Search terms include "Heritage Science", "Cultural Heritage", and "Digital Cultural Heritage" • scientific articles in open access journals: <i>Journal of Cultural Heritage</i> • scientific articles and sector-specific conference proceedings: <i>Computer Applications in Archaeology</i> • sector-specific conference proceedings: <i>ArcheoFOSS</i>
LANDSCAPING TOOLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • H2IOSC Landscaping Questionnaire • Spreadsheet for data entry, management, and retrieval • Keyword-based search of source materials • Web App: DHeLO - Digital Heritage Landscaping Platform • Zotero BiDiAr collection
RESOURCES INFORMATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authors • Research institutions • Research projects • Datasets linked to research projects • Tools for the creation, visualization, management, and reprocessing of data

Table 7: E-RIHS.it Landscape criteria

Landscape Sources

SSHOC MarketPlace

The SSH Open Marketplace is a key resource for identifying and contextualizing tools, datasets, training materials, services, workflows, and publications relevant to the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) research community. It provides an accessible, user-oriented portal where researchers can find digital solutions to support all phases of the research data lifecycle in SSH.

The SSH Open Marketplace is built around five main content types:

- Tools and services
- Training materials
- Workflows
- Datasets
- Publications

CLARIN VLO

The CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory (VLO) is a discovery platform that provides unified access to a wide range of language resources, including corpora, lexical databases, metadata records, and language tools deposited in the various CLARIN certified repositories distributed across Europe. Built on a metadata harvesting and aggregation framework, the VLO allows researchers to search, browse, and filter resources according to multiple facets such as language, resource type, modality, or license. By exposing interoperable metadata compliant with CLARIN standards (Melaccio et al., 2025), the VLO facilitates cross-resource comparability and supports the findability and accessibility dimensions of the FAIR principles. As a central access point, the VLO plays a strategic role in enabling scholars from diverse research (sub-)communities to discover and reuse resources beyond disciplinary and geographic boundaries.

DARIAH-EU Tool and Services Catalogue

In September 2023, DARIAH officially launched the DARIAH Tools and Services Catalogue, now accessible through both the DARIAH website and the SSH Open Marketplace. The catalogue features over 200 resources and distinguishes between two main types of services: Core Services and Community Services. Core Services are owned and managed by DARIAH-ERIC and delivered through its national nodes; they represent the infrastructure backbone and strategic mission. Community Services, on the other hand, are maintained by one or more DARIAH partner institutions and typically support local capacity building and research instrumentation.

The DARIAH Tools and Services Catalogue serves as a central access point for exploring the rich landscape of digital resources offered by the DARIAH infrastructure. The catalogue does not represent the full internal portfolio of DARIAH services but is rather a curated selection of those deemed suitable for public listing. It offers a user-friendly interface that allows scholars to discover, access, and evaluate available digital resources. As of now, the catalogue

includes 29 contributions from DARIAH-IT, further illustrating the active involvement of national nodes in the provision of reusable and open-access research tools.

6.2 Knowledge Organization Schema

The adopted methodology focused on developing a structured system for organizing and describing resources, with attention to their typology, stage within the data lifecycle, data formats, applicable standards, and disciplinary characteristics. While devising the mapping strategy, attention was also placed on their alignment with the FAIR principles: how easily resources can be found, accessed, integrated, and reused across contexts.

This activity involved a systematic collection of information on both datasets and digital tools, drawing on inputs provided by the participating Work Packages and affiliated institutions. Resources were described using a shared metadata framework to enable comparative analysis and consistent evaluation. In the case of datasets, emphasis was placed on aspects such as content type, disciplinary scope, availability, data stewardship, and adherence to recognized standards. For digital tools and services, the analysis focused on their core functionalities, technical attributes, stage of development, and their ability to interact with or enhance relevant datasets.

The metadata framework incorporates essential descriptive elements, including basic resource information, technical characteristics (such as supported input/output formats and compliance with standards), institutional ownership, and possible links to other Pilots or research infrastructures. This mapping exercise offers a structured and integrated perspective on both existing and emerging digital resources, while also highlighting external assets that may be suitable for integration or alignment with the project's strategic objectives (Table 8).

Field	Description	Datasets	Tools
ID	Identifier for internal reference	X	X
Name	full name (expanded acronym)	X	X
Acronym	Or short name of the project	X	X
Title	To be added to the name if provided	X	X
Type of dataset	classification of the dataset (e.g., corpus, glossary, image repository, edition, etc.)	X	
Type of tool	classification of the tool (e.g., annotation tool, data management system, learning system, visualization platform, etc.)		X
Description	type of information conveyed; content included in the datasets / main features, details about the context of use	X	X
Native data access tool	how are the data accessed? If available online, specify the name of the tool used	X	

	to access them (preferably also include the tool in the tools list)		
Link (to web instance or website)	link to the download page if available, or to the online instance	X	
Link to the tool	link to the download page if available, or to the online instance		X
Last update (optional)	Date format		X
Offered services / functionalities	details on the type(s) of supported services, e.g., DBMS, KB, LMS, ML, etc.		X
Relevant disciplines	Relevant discipline: academic or research domain(s) to which the dataset or tool is related (e.g., linguistics, philology, archaeology, lexicography, art history, heritage science, digital humanities, etc.)	X	X
Documentation	Documentation: link to user manuals, technical documentation, or descriptive materials related to the dataset or tool		X
Involved Research Infrastructure (RI)	infrastructure that contributed to the development	X	X
Responsible institution/center	name of the institution, research center, or organization in charge of maintaining or overseeing the dataset or tool	X	X
Curator	name of the individual or institution responsible for the curation, maintenance, or scholarly oversight of the dataset	X	
Contact person	if different from the curator / whom to contact for clarifications; not necessarily the developer	X	
File format (extension)	format or extension of the files stored in the dataset (e.g., .xml, .csv, .json, .xlsx, .txt, .rdf, etc.)	X	
Data model/standard	conceptual model or formal standard used to structure the data (e.g., CIDOC CRM, TEI, Dublin Core, EAD, METS, etc.)	X	
Programming language (optional)	programming language(s) used to develop or implement the tool (e.g., Python, Java, PHP, JavaScript, etc.)		X
Link to source code (if available)	e.g., on GitHub		X
Developer / Responsible center	individual, institution, company, or development team responsible for creating the tool		X
Developer contact (optional)	contact information for the developer or development team responsible for the tool		X
Input data format(s) (file extension)	file extension of the input (e.g., xml, csv, xlsx, dtd, txt, etc.)		X

Required data standards	standard followed by the input data (e.g., TEI, ICCD, EAD, EAC, etc.)		X
Status	developed or under development		X
Usable datasets	datasets that can be processed, accessed, or integrated by the tool (include names, links, or references where applicable)		X
Output data format	file extension of the output (e.g., xml, csv, xlsx, dtd, txt, etc.)		X
Provided data standards	standard followed by the output data (e.g., TEI, ICCD, EAD, EAC, etc.)		X
Link to Pilot (for internal H2IOSC use)	Reference to the H2IOSC Pilot the resource can be compared to	X	X
Notes	additional remarks, contextual information, or clarifications relevant to the dataset or tool that do not fit into other fields	X	X
Priority	relevance or urgency level assigned to the dataset or tool within the project context (low, medium, high)	X	X

Table 8: Fields and Metadata of tables of Datasets and Tools

To develop a unified framework for resource mapping within the H2IOSC project, WP2 began analyzing the respective needs to develop a unified strategy. While each RIs differed in scope and disciplinary focus, they revealed several common themes, including the need to document resource status, development context, disciplinary relevance, and FAIRness aspects.

The Knowledge Organization Schema provides the conceptual and structural basis for organising the landscape tables, allowing for the systematic classification of resources according to their typology, stage within the data lifecycle, technical characteristics, and degree of FAIR alignment. The mapping and analysis activities carried out within WP2 laid the groundwork for understanding the heterogeneous landscape of research infrastructures, resources, and user needs across the domains of humanities, language sciences, and heritage science in Italy. The process has highlighted the diversity of data types, access modalities, and disciplinary cultures, prompting an initial harmonisation effort to align perspectives and expectations across domains.

The results of WP2 didn't remain confined to internal reporting but have actively fed into the development of key strategic assets of the H2IOSC infrastructure. The collected data and reports have been incorporated into the design of the H2IOSC Marketplace, where they inform the classification, onboarding, and presentation of resources and services in a way that reflects the real needs and practices of the research communities. Furthermore, they constitute the informational foundation of the H2IOSC Observatory, a permanent knowledge space dedicated to monitoring communities, identifying trends, and tracking evolving training

and technological demands. WP2 Permanent Observatory (§7) acts as an interface between analysis and infrastructure, ensuring that strategic foresight remains embedded in platform development.

A concrete outcome of the landscaping process is the development of DHeLO - Digital Humanities Enhanced Learning Observatory, a platform that leverages the knowledge base generated by WP2 to support exploration, discovery, and visualisation of disciplinary resources and user needs. DHeLO exemplifies how landscaping results can be transformed into operational tools supporting both the community and platform designers.

WP2 also established robust interdependencies with the other Project's Work Packages, sharing data, frameworks, and survey results. It collaborated with WP6 in identifying and describing available services; contributed to WP4 in the definition of the resources to be included in the semantic framework; cooperated with WP5 in shaping onboarding strategies for the Marketplace; and worked with WP7 in aligning the landscaping results with pilot implementation. This demonstrates the central role of WP2 as both an analytical and integrative component of the project, enabling the operational reuse of its outputs across the entire H2IOSC ecosystem.

6.3 Unified H2IOSC Landscape criteria and methods

These standardized metadata fields were then organized into three dedicated spreadsheets:

- Pilot Requirements, aligned with WP7, capture the functional needs of the Pilots and their expected tools or services.
- Landscaping Tools, used by WP6, WP7, and WP8, lists software, services, and platforms relevant to the project.
- Landscaping Datasets, aligned with WP6, and WP7, focuses on structured data resources used or produced by the community.

Each sheet is structured into thematic sections: *General Information*, *Development*, *Input/Output Data*, *Curation*, and *Interconnections*, with fields derived from the original RI criteria. For example, mentions of "status," "developer," and "programming language" were formalized under a *Development* section, while references to "disciplines," "projects," and "repository presence" informed the *General Information* and *Interconnections* fields.

The adoption of this structured template allowed WP2 to harmonise metadata, thus ensuring that the information provided by the various RIs and WPs remained comparable, reusable, and interoperable. This common schema supports both the mapping effort and the broader goals of WP2 to achieve landscaping of the whole Federation.

The organization of this activity is detailed in the following paragraphs, which explain the sheets prepared to carry out the WP2 mapping.

Pilot Requirements

This sheet gathers the requirements of the Pilots from the four infrastructures, as described by WP7, that are of interest for WP2. The objective of this analysis is to create a comprehensive list of requirements, useful for identifying shared development goals and highlighting interconnections and overlaps that may arise during the project.

Fields

Section: General Information includes:

- *Reference Pilot*: the name of the reference pilot (selected from a drop-down menu);
- *Task*: the related task (drop-down menu);
- *RI*: the reference research infrastructure (drop-down menu);
- *Description*: a brief description of the Pilot's requirement;
- *Status*: the development status (drop-down menu), which can be "Developed" (indicating a product already available), "Under development" (a product currently in progress but not yet in production), or "Not developed" (a product required by the Pilot but whose development has not yet started).

Section: If Developed or Under Development (to be completed if the "Status" field is "Developed" or "Under development"):

- *Development percentage*: approximate percentage of the tool's development completion;
- *Developer*: the institute, university, or company responsible for the tool's development;
- *Link to the tool*: webpage link where the tool is available;
- *Link to the code (if available)*: link to the GitHub/GOGS/Jupyter repository containing the tool's code.

Section: If Not Developed (to be completed if "Status" is "Not developed"):

- *Development approach*: specifies whether development is handled internally within the project or outsourced through an external tender.

Section: Reports and Interconnections includes:

- *Link to other Pilots*: indicating whether the tool may be of interest to other Pilots beyond the one that produced it;

- *Contact person*: contact details of the person responsible for the entry;
- *Report of already developed products*: indication of external tools (outside the project) known to satisfy the Pilot's requirement;
- *Notes*: field for comments or remarks.

Landscaping Tools

This sheet allows the relevant Work Packages (WP2, WP6, WP7, WP8) to report tools and services relevant to the objectives of each WP and of the H2IOSC project. The entries may refer to products developed within the Operative Units (OUs) involved in the project, as well as those developed externally.

Fields

Section: General Information includes:

- *ID*: a sequential number that uniquely identifies the resource;
- *Name*: name of the resource;
- *Description*: brief description of the resource;
- *Link to the tool*: webpage link where the resource is available;
- *Last update*: date of the most recent update;
- *Offered services*: types of services provided (e.g. data analysis, NLP, NER, controlled vocabularies, etc.);
- *Relevant disciplines*: research areas for which the resource was designed (e.g. linguistics, archaeology, lexicography, legal studies, etc.);
- *Reference WP*: the Work Package responsible for entering the resource into the sheet;
- *RI*: whether the resource was developed within one of the research infrastructures involved in the project or is otherwise available in the corresponding marketplaces.

Section: Development includes:

- *Status*: development status (drop-down menu: Developed, Under development, Not developed);
- *Development percentage*: approximate percentage of completion;
- *Developer*: institute, university, company, or individual responsible for development;
- *Developer contact*: email contact of the developer;
- *Programming language*: programming language(s) used to develop the resource;
- *Link to the code (if available)*: GitHub/GOGS repository link containing the tool's code.

Section: Input Data includes:

- *Input data format*: format of the data accepted by the resource;

- *Required data standards*: standards required for the resource to accept input data.

Section: Output Data includes:

- *Output data format*: format of the data produced by the resource;
- *Provided data standards*: standards used in the output data.

Section: Interconnections includes:

- *Link to Pilots*: whether the tool was developed within a Pilot or may be of interest to one;
- *Contact person*: contact details of the person responsible for the entry;
- *Notes*: field for comments or remarks.

Landscaping Datasets

This sheet is used by the relevant Work Packages (WP2, WP6, WP7) to report datasets relevant to the objectives of each WP and the H2IOSC project. The entries may refer to datasets produced within the Operative Units (OUs) involved in the project as well as those produced externally.

Fields

Section: General Information includes:

- *ID*: a sequential number that uniquely identifies the dataset;
- *Name*: dataset name;
- *Description*: brief description of the dataset;
- *Native data access tool*: name and, if applicable, link to the native tool for accessing the dataset;
- *Link*: link for accessing or downloading the dataset;
- *Relevant disciplines*: research areas for which the dataset was designed (e.g. linguistics, archaeology, lexicography, legal studies, etc.);
- *Reference WP*: Work Package responsible for entering the dataset;
- *RI*: whether the dataset was developed within one of the research infrastructures involved in the project, or is available through their respective marketplaces.

Section: Curation includes:

- *Curator*: name of the institution or person responsible for curating the data;
- *Curator link*: link to the web page of the data curator;
- *Curator description*: brief description of the data curator;

- *Curator contact*: email contact of the curator (for institutions or organisations, a contact person is provided).

Section: Development Context and Data includes:

- *Development context*: description of the context and purpose for which the dataset was created;
- *Data format*: format of the dataset;
- *Data standards*: standards to which the data conform.

Section: Interconnections includes:

- *Link to Pilots*: indication of whether the dataset may be of interest to a Pilot;
- *Contact person*: contact of the person responsible for the entry;
- *Notes*: field for comments or remarks.

Once the WP2 agreed upon the general strategy and the fields to be highlighted in the analysis according to this description, the tables to gather information about tools and datasets in the Humanities and Heritage sectors were prepared.

7. Digital Heritage Landscaping PlatfOrm: DHeLO

A significant part of the project's objectives concerned external landscaping activities. Unlike other scientific domains, in the fields of Heritage Science (HS) and Digital Cultural Heritage (DCH) there was no dedicated platform capable of systematically mapping, evaluating, and querying research outputs and infrastructures. To address this gap, a platform called DHeLO (Digital Heritage Landscaping platform) was developed and progressively refined over the course of the project (Mancuso and D'Eredità in press; Mancuso et al. 2025; Mancuso 2025; Mancuso and D'Eredità 2024; Luzietti et al. 2024). Originally conceived as a web-based SQL database (§ 7.1), it later evolved into a Linked Open Data (LOD) system to enhance semantic interoperability and data reuse (§ 7.3 and § 7.4).

At its core, DHeLO is a web application developed as part of the landscaping activities of the H2IOSC Project. Its main objective is to collect, store, and query metadata related to research projects, digital products, and tools used in the CH and CHS domains. The platform was conceived as a first, concrete step toward the development of a disciplinary observatory—a centralized infrastructure capable of aggregating metadata from diverse sources in a structured and interoperable way, enabling complex queries, indexing, and retrieval operations.

The need for such a system emerged during the early phases of Work Package 2 (WP2), particularly from insights gathered through the project's initial questionnaire (Luzietti et al.). The responses highlighted the absence of standardized practices for data production and management, as well as the extreme heterogeneity of data formats (e.g., images, texts, tables, surveys, point clouds) and structures. This context guided the decision to focus on datasets rather than individual resources, since the latter would have required the design of complex, domain-specific ontologies.

Further investigation revealed that no existing platforms could adequately serve as a disciplinary observatory. Broader aggregators like Europeana or CulturalItalia were excluded due to their focus on individual items and lack of metadata granularity, while others such as Ariadne+ or Zenodo either applied overly generic metadata schemas or were too thematically constrained.

In response, DHeLO was designed to both enrich metadata for existing open datasets and include references to non-digitally deposited resources described in scholarly literature. It aimed to offer a snapshot of what is currently being produced or made available digitally within the CH and HS sectors. Essential components of the system include a thematic classification of research products, chronological and geographical indexing, and an interoperable metadata schema based on the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI). The platform also integrates RESTful JSON APIs to facilitate metadata harvesting, external reuse, and interoperability with other services such as DIGILAB and the Open Digital Archaeology and Epigraphy Hubs.

7.1 DHeLO 1.0. A technical overview of the data model

From a technical standpoint, the version 1.0 of the web app consisted of a MySQL database with an HTML interface that can be used for data entry and retrieval (Fig. 25).

Figure 25: Screenshot of the DHeLO 1.0 interface.

The database was organized into six main tables, with the ‘Products’ table serving as the core component. In this context, ‘Products’ (as in research products) refer to datasets or collections of datasets that are grouped together based on a shared framework, such as chronological period or geographic region (Fig. 26; Table 9). This solution recalls the approach used by Zenodo for managing user datasets. In this specific case it proves particularly efficient because it does not limit the ability to input data in the system based on specific and individual data types, allowing the possibility to index complex products made of multiple kinds of resources (e.g. database with images or 3D models with semantic annotations).

Within the ‘Products’ table, additional metadata are entered to facilitate the indexing and the retrieval of items. These include classification and subject matter, data ownership, licensing details, the location of data storage (if data are shared), research projects, and bibliographic references describing them. For the classification tags, it was decided to test the criteria developed using Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Machine Learning techniques on the abstracts from the journal «Archeologia e Calcolatori» (Caravale et al. 2023), since CH/HS

disciplinary topics are broadly represented both in the journal and in DHeLO. Ultimately, this choice proved effective, even though some of the classes seem poorly represented within DHeLO; additional subject details are also provided by the ‘Subject’ field. This dual-layered approach, a long-term strategy within the A&C journal (Moscatti 1999), ensures a comprehensive description that captures the technological aspect, provided by the ‘Category’ field, while contextualizing its disciplinary applications within the ‘Subject’ field.

Figure 26: Overview of the DHeLO table schema structure

For bibliographic references, only a link to the Zotero library of BiDiAr (§ 7.6) is included. The approach of linking to an external Zotero library streamlines bibliographic management, allowing for dynamic updates and centralized reference handling. This method also simplifies the maintenance of the reference data, making it easier for users to access up-to-date bibliographic information. For geographical and chronological classification, the system relies on two gazetteers: Pleiades and PeriodO. By referencing gazetteers, accuracy and standardization in geographic and temporal data are ensured, a critical aspect for chronological and spatial query. Similar to the solution adopted for the bibliography, these data are contained in relation tables, which allow the construction of many-to-many relationships, enabling the precise indexing of datasets that contain references to multiple places, periods, or are described by multiple bibliographic resources. The authorship of the dataset is described through two distinct fields that map the curation and production aspects; both fields draw data from the ‘People’ table. The technical contents of the records in the ‘Product’ table are further detailed through a second table called ‘Product Type,’ in which the different types of products that make up the dataset are specified. This additional table allows for a more nuanced classification and management of the information, so, for instance, a

photogrammetric survey product record can be further detailed in all the data types that were created during the process (e.g. pictures, point cloud, mesh, 3D model) and shared. Due to the relationship with the 'Product' table, the individual types of products that make up the dataset inherit their metadata and are thus individually indexable and searchable enhancing the database's overall functionality and user experience in conducting searches based on data types over specific territorial or chronological frameworks. All the product types that make up the dataset can be further detailed through a many-to-many relationship with the 'Tools' table, that records the digital tools used for the creation, display, or interaction with the data. The 'Tools' table then records several important pieces of information about the type of tool (e.g., software, plugin, web-app), its availability, its license and its developers. This setup enhances the database's utility by providing comprehensive details on the technological aspects of product data handling, allowing, for instance, to assess the prevalence of open-source software in relation to different product types.

The 'Project' table, which is closely linked to the 'Products' table, is designed to gather information on research projects. This table records various details such as the project's title and acronym, a brief description, its duration, the reference website, and the people involved. The relationship between this table and the products allows the records in this table to act as an umbrella under which all products developed during a single research project are collected. This structure enhances the organization and tracking of outputs directly associated with specific research initiatives. Two additional tables, 'People' and 'Institutions', are used to track the individuals and institutions involved in the creation of products, projects, and tools. The 'People' table contains basic personal information (name, surname, email) easily accessible online. It also allows for linking a contact record with the corresponding institution and the author's ORCID to facilitate future automatic updates.

The 'Institutions' table focuses on the department or institute, and maps out details including the institution, department, and the associated website, providing a comprehensive reference for each entity involved in the database (Annex 3.1).

7.2 DHeLO Data collection process

The data collection process began with scraping the products and research projects carried out by the ISPC and the E-RHIS infrastructure, along with the incorporation of results from the landscaping questionnaire launched in the early phases of WP2. Data was subsequently gathered from major data-sharing platforms relevant to the disciplines of CH/HS, such as Zenodo, Ariadne+, HS-Openaire, Iperion HS, AdS, tDAR, and OpenContext. Following this, the parsing process was continued based on sector-specific literature, focusing primarily on works from the last five years, to reflect an updated state of the art. For the Digital Archaeology (DA) field were considered products described in peer-reviewed journals such as «Archeologia e Calcolatori», «Virtual Archaeology Review», «Open Archaeology», and «Internet Archaeology». An in-depth focus on Digital CH was achieved by indexing products from the «Journal of Cultural Heritage» and «Digital Applications in Archaeology and Cultural

Heritage», while the HS domain was explored through «Heritage Science» and «Heritage» journals. Additionally sector-specific proceeding series (e.g. Computer Application in Archaeology, MetroArchaeo) within the last five years were considered.

During this process, due to H2IOSC Project requirements, priority was given to Italian research products, with consideration also given to those developed abroad, but when conducted by Italian researchers or research groups.

7.3 DHeLO 2.0. - A technical overview

During the project, reflections stemming from the analysis of the questionnaire data and the interviews made it increasingly clear that DHeLO could assume a more active role within the broader landscape of research infrastructures. An idea that gradually took shape during the platform's development phase, and was later reinforced through several interviews, was the potential value of a system capable of aggregating and thematically, geographically, and chronologically indexing existing datasets, interactive resources, and research projects. It became evident that DHeLO could move beyond functioning solely as a passive virtual observatory operating behind the scenes, evolving instead into an active service for the community. The envisioned system would not require contributors to adhere to a rigid data model; rather, it would focus on collecting and exposing digital resources already available online, in diverse formats, and making them accessible through a unified, searchable interface, thus addressing a gap identified within the current infrastructure ecosystem (see further §4 on survey results).

The transition from a relational database to a service-oriented infrastructure designed for the broader research community called for a partial reconfiguration of DHeLO. Rather than a full restructuring, this shift marked a progressive alignment with LOD principles, aiming to improve interoperability, discoverability, and semantic integration (<https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>). This new perspective made it easier to map and contextualise resources that are often available online with only minimal or generic metadata or whose descriptive elements are accessible exclusively through associated scholarly literature. Structuring the platform around LOD-compatible logics offered a way to capture and represent such resources more effectively, while maintaining a lightweight, inclusive approach to aggregation. This conceptual transition was accompanied by a substantial rethinking of the technical infrastructure supporting DHeLO (Fig. 27).

DHeLO

Digital Heritage Landscaping platfOrm

Projects

This section gathers a curated collection of **research projects** that have contributed to the field of **cultural heritage and heritage science** by producing **digital outputs** such as datasets, interactive resources, or specialized tools. By structuring metadata on these projects, DHeLO helps to **connect research activities** and make their digital contributions more accessible and reusable.

You can explore the projects in different ways:

- **Through the interactive graph**, which visualizes relationships between projects and their digital outputs.
- **Using the timeline**, which allows you to track the chronological progression of research initiatives.
- **By exploring the catalog alphabetically**, offering an organized way to browse through the projects.
- **Via the search module**, which enables you to find specific projects based on keywords, titles, or other relevant metadata.

Each of these tools provides a distinct perspective, offering a comprehensive way to navigate and analyze the **landscape of digital research** in cultural heritage.

Network graph of:

Research Projects and Their Digital Outputs

Figure 27: Project page on DHeLO 2.0

After evaluating a number of alternatives (such as Arches, used in the configuration of the ISPC dataspace), it was decided to migrate the system to Omeka S, an open-source web publishing platform developed by the Digital Scholar project at the Roy Rosenzweig Center for History and New Media, based at George Mason University (<https://rrchnm.org/>). Omeka S (<https://omeka.org/s/>) is the evolution of the original Omeka Classic software (<https://omeka.org/classic/>), and was designed to support multi-site environments, semantic interoperability, and the management of digital objects across multiple contexts; functioning as a content management system (CMS) and allowing for both structured data handling and visual customisation via templates and CSS.

At its core, Omeka S provides a powerful yet user-friendly backend for managing structured metadata, as well as a flexible publishing layer for creating public-facing sites that present digital collections in curated and accessible ways. Notably, the platform can be managed effectively by users with no specific technical background, making it especially suitable for collaborative and multidisciplinary environments. While commonly adopted in the digital humanities and museum sectors, its use in DA project is still limited, though steadily increasing. One of the key advantages that Omeka S provided to DHeLO lies in its modular

architecture. Through an ecosystem of plugins and extensions, it was possible to integrate advanced functionalities without compromising the system's core structure. Among these add-ons, one of the features that most strongly influenced the choice toward this software was the Collecting module, which allows users to submit metadata for content to be ingested into the system. This capability is particularly significant, as it enables broader community participation while contributing to the long-term sustainability of the platform. This functionality envisions a future where DHeLO could become partially sustained through user-submitted content, curated and published with minimal editorial oversight by a restricted editorial board. This orientation aligns DHeLO with emerging models of participatory infrastructures, where communities are not only users but also contributors to the growth, curation, and sustainability of shared digital ecosystems.

Another compelling reason for choosing Omeka S is its close conceptual and institutional affinity with Zotero, the widely used reference management tool (www.zotero.org). Both platforms were developed within the same institutional framework, and share a commitment to openness, usability, and sustainability. In the context of the H2IOSC project, this synergy was particularly valuable given the relationship between DHeLO and BiDiAr, a bibliographic database originally built with Zotero (see further), and soon to be imported into Omeka S. The possibility of cross-platform integration, particularly in terms of metadata reuse and synchronisation, positioned Omeka S as a natural solution for supporting the long-term development of both platforms within a shared ecosystem. Additionally, Omeka S includes built-in RESTful APIs, which facilitate programmatic access to the data and support interoperability with external systems and services. This feature aligns closely with current recommendations on infrastructural openness and machine-actionability and allowed to exploit DHeLO's data for the Open Digital Archaeology Hub (see further). Equally important in the selection process was Omeka S's native support for controlled vocabularies and ontology-based metadata structures. The platform is designed to work natively with RDF-compliant ontologies and supports the import of external vocabularies expressed in SKOS or OWL. It allows seamless alignment with widely adopted semantic standards such as Dublin Core, FOAF, and schema.org, and – especially relevant for the archaeological domain – with CIDOC CRM, which is increasingly recognised as a reference model for the representation of CH data. In this respect, the contribution of the H-Setis platform, developed within the project to collect and share semantic resources and ontologies within the HS an CH domain, was instrumental in defining a conceptual and technical framework of the new DHeLO infrastructure, compliant with disciplinary domain standards.

7.4 DHeLO 2.0 - Adjusting the data model

As previously mentioned (§7.3) the shift to a LOD infrastructure brought with it a partial reorganisation of DHeLO's underlying data model. A close analysis of the existing entities revealed a high degree of correspondence with classes defined in two widely adopted ontologies: FOAF and the DCTerms. These vocabularies, while relatively lightweight, provide

a robust and widely compatible foundation for describing agents, organisations, intellectual outputs, and related entities. Accordingly, the core tables were mapped to the following classes: *foaf:Person* for individuals; *foaf:Organization* for institutions; *dctype:Software* and *dctype:Dataset* for tools and research products, respectively; and *foaf:Project* for research initiatives. One important refinement emerged during this reconfiguration: the introduction of *dctype:InteractiveResource* as a distinct class to represent digital assets that serve as interfaces for accessing data — such as visualisation platforms, WebGIS portals, or multimedia exploration tools. In the previous model, these resources had been grouped under the general category of ‘tools’, a choice that inadvertently reduced their intellectual specificity and made it difficult to establish precise relationships with other entities in the system. By assigning them to a dedicated semantic class, it became possible to capture their dual nature as both access mechanisms and scholarly outputs, and to situate them more meaningfully within the larger graph of research activities and digital production. Importantly, this semantic distinction also enabled these resources to benefit from the same thematic, geographic, and chronological indexing strategies applied to datasets — a crucial step in enhancing their visibility and interoperability within the platform.

The thematic classification system adopted in DHeLO remained consistent with the previous version of the platform. It continues to draw on the taxonomy developed by the journal *Archeologia e Calcolatori*, which offers a well-established and domain-specific framework for categorising research products in the field of archaeological computing. As for spatial and temporal metadata, the system had already adopted a gazetteer-based approach in its earlier implementation, and this strategy was retained in the current version. However, it was observed that in order to enable certain advanced visualisation features, such as interactive maps and timelines, it would be preferable to structure spatial and temporal references as independent items within the data model. For this purpose, two additional classes were introduced: *dcterms:Location* and *dcterms:PeriodOfTime*, which serve as containers for geographic and chronological metadata imported from external gazetteers. On the temporal side, this approach ensured continuity with the use of the PeriodO gazetteer. On the spatial side, it opened the possibility of integrating and combining data from multiple gazetteers, thereby addressing a potential limitation in relying solely on a single source, such as Pleiades, where certain locations might not be represented. The introduction of dedicated items for places and periods not only improved the precision of metadata but also enhanced the platform’s ability to support semantic linking, filtering, and visual exploration of resources across time and space.

Figure 28: Entity relationship schema for DHeLO 2.0.

Finally, the bibliographic references associated with the various entities are drawn from the BiDiAr system and include links to their corresponding Zotero records, allowing for rapid consultation and reuse.

The following table lists the metadata fields used for the main resource classes structured within the DHeLO platform (Table 10). Each class is described according to a set of standardized properties that ensure semantic clarity and interoperability. For a complete overview of the DHeLO data model and its implementation, please refer to the [official documentation](#) (see also: Annex 3.2).

7.5 Results overview

The activities carried out during the reporting period have contributed to consolidating DHeLO as a key infrastructure for the collection, organization, and dissemination of digital resources in the wider domains of Digital Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science. Beyond the technical improvements, the platform has been enriched with a diversified corpus of data, thus providing researchers and practitioners with a broader and more representative basis for their work.

Importantly, DHeLO itself should also be regarded as one of the main outputs of the landscaping process undertaken within WP2. By systematically gathering, harmonizing, and exposing resources, the platform not only documents the current landscape of digital practices but also enables their further development in terms of interoperability, accessibility, and reuse.

The platform, already accessible at <https://dhelo.cnr.it>, is fully operational and available to the community. This ensures that the outcomes of the landscaping activity are not confined to an internal testing phase but are instead offered as an open tool for immediate consultation and use by researchers and institutions.

In particular, the platform has been populated with a wide range of resources, reflecting both the heterogeneity of the cultural heritage record and the multiple needs of the research community. The data currently available include (fig. 29; 30):

- Dataset (175)

- Interactive Resources (100)
- Projects (183)
- Softwares (81)
- Locations (386)
- Periods (101)
- Organizations (298)
- People (1074)

Figure 29: Quantities of data collected in DHeLO, broken down by type of entity.

Figure 30: Geographic distribution of the resources collected within DHeLO, visualized through the platform's mapping interface.

Taken as a whole, the results achieved demonstrate the capacity of WP2 to generate both conceptual and technical tools in support of the Digital Cultural Heritage and Heritage Science communities. They also provide a foundation for further developments in the framework of H2IOSC and beyond, in line with the principles of Open Science and FAIR data management. In this perspective, the data collected through DHeLO will also be harvested and made available within the WP2 Permanent Observatory (§8), ensuring their long-term visibility and integration into a broader monitoring environment.

7.6 BiDiAr - Bibliography of Digital Archaeology

In recognition of the continuing centrality of bibliographic resources as the primary means of scholarly communication within the research community – as emerged from the interviews – particular importance was assigned on the management of scientific bibliography in the fields of DA, CH, and HS. This attention led to the creation of BiDiAr, conceived both as a tool for deepening the understanding of disciplinary dynamics and as a service-oriented resource for the broader research community. BiDiAr was designed as a database, aimed at systematically collecting, organizing, and thematically indexing bibliographic metadata of sector-relevant publications. The platform's primary objective is to ensure accessibility, thematic classification, and long-term preservation of references critical to the development of these disciplinary areas. The ambition behind BiDiAr is not to create a bibliometric tool, but rather to develop a platform that facilitates the sharing, use, and reuse of bibliographic resources. By accelerating the production of scholarly articles and supporting the thematic exploration

of existing literature, BiDiAr aims to foster the discovery of new connections and research directions within the DA and CH communities.

Analogous to the iterative development process of DHeLO, the design of BiDiAr evolved during the project, adapting to the needs that emerged both from community feedback and from the evolving specifications of the infrastructure. The first implementation of BiDiAr was based on Zotero, a widely adopted open-source bibliographic management tool selected for its collaborative features, harvesting capabilities, and increasing acceptance within the scholarly publishing ecosystem. The choice aligns with methodologies adopted by other European research infrastructures, such as DARIAH, and reflects practices increasingly common in projects like [EAGLE](#) or [PATHS](#). Zotero's flexibility, together with its capacity to generate unique URLs for each record, has been particularly advantageous for bibliographic management within a LOD approach. Currently, BiDiAr aggregates bibliographic records across four principal categories: 1) articles published in *Archeologia e Calcolatori* between 1990 and 2024, including both regular issues and Supplements (over 1,300 records); 2) all bibliographic references cited within the articles published in A&C volumes from 2019 to 2024, totalling approximately 10,000 entries; 3) references associated with datasets indexed in DHeLO, incorporated as external links; and 4) references related to the thematic collections included in the Open Digital Archaeology Hub (see further).

The close integration between BiDiAr and DHeLO is prompting a significant evolution of the system. A migration process is currently underway to incorporate BiDiAr into DHeLO's Omeka S environment, with metadata structured according to the Bibliographic Ontology (BIBO). This transition, although technically demanding, aims to achieve a unified management of research data within the infrastructure and to align the bibliographic repository with semantic web standards. The adoption of a knowledge graph model will allow not only for enhanced retrieval and exploration of bibliographic resources, but also for the dynamic integration of metadata across research outputs, projects, and datasets. Through this transformation, BiDiAr is positioned to evolve from a traditional bibliographic archive into an active component of an interconnected, semantically enriched research ecosystem. This approach, centered on the semantic enrichment and interconnection of research outputs, also underpins the design philosophy of the ArchaeoHub (Mancuso 2025; Caravale et al. 2025), which aims to further consolidate and expand the networked knowledge environment with a focus on DA.

8. H2IOSC Observatory

8.1 Concept and general aims

The H2IOSC Permanent Observatory is one of the flagship components of H2IOSC, designed to monitor, analyse, and valorise the ecosystem of research infrastructures, services, and user practices that converge within the H2IOSC federation. Conceived as a digital and methodological instrument, the Observatory complements the H2IOSC Marketplace, acting as an evidence-based interface for understanding how data, tools, and communities interact within an open science environment (Sichera et al., 2025). It is both a scientific output and an operational tool that informs the design of policies, infrastructures, and services aligned with the principles of openness, interoperability, and sustainability.

The Observatory emerges from the integrated mixed-methods approach developed in Work Package 2, which combines quantitative surveys, one-to-one interviews, focus groups, and semi-automatic data collection protocols. The results and insights produced through these instruments are made publicly accessible through a dynamic and continuously updated web application, providing a structured and transparent environment for the dissemination of evidence-based analyses. In this sense, the Observatory operates as a permanent and reflexive mechanism that supports the strategic evolution of the H2IOSC infrastructure over time.

8.2 Structure, scope, and positioning

Like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Observatory, but with a more targeted and granular focus, the H2IOSC Observatory serves as an intelligence platform for the continuous monitoring of research practices, resource usage, and community needs within the H2IOSC ecosystem. It provides an integrated analytical perspective on how data resources, digital instruments, and users interact in practice, offering a multidimensional view that connects the technological, organisational, and cultural dimensions of research infrastructures.

The Observatory includes a public interactive dashboard that allows users to explore visualisations and metrics concerning research data, tools, and community activities. These insights directly inform the development and uptake of H2IOSC nodes and services, helping identify emerging gaps, prioritise the FAIRification of resources, and design strategies for integrating new datasets and tools into the Marketplace. Unlike traditional landscape analyses or static observatories—where methodologies and data sources often remain opaque—the H2IOSC Observatory is grounded in the replicable and validated instruments tested in WP2, ensuring transparency, methodological rigour, and accountability to the communities that contribute data.

Figure 31: The H2IOSC Observatory home page

8.3 Methodological approach and system design

The design of the Observatory follows a user-centered and evidence-driven approach, grounded in principles of accessibility, clarity, and methodological robustness. Its development involves close collaboration between research teams, data engineers, and UX/UI specialists, ensuring coherence between scientific objectives and technological implementation. The methodological backbone of the Observatory combines statistical analysis with qualitative interpretation, enabling the representation of complex, multidimensional realities in a comprehensible and visually coherent form.

From a technical standpoint, the Observatory is implemented as a modular web application developed in synergy with the H2IOSC Marketplace. The two platforms are interconnected, establishing a bidirectional flow of information: while the Marketplace aggregates and exposes digital resources, the Observatory analyses their use and evolution, returning insights that guide further development. This dynamic relationship ensures that data collected from user interactions are continuously integrated into the federation’s broader strategic framework.

The UX/UI design ensures usability across a diverse audience of researchers, infrastructure managers, and policy makers. The interface adopts a minimalist and institutional aesthetic, aligned with H2IOSC’s visual identity and compliant with the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG). A modular architecture allows for independent management of each

thematic section while maintaining overall coherence, guaranteeing long-term maintainability and scalability.

8.4 Information architecture and content organisation

The Observatory's information architecture accommodates both the diversity of data types and the heterogeneity of user profiles. It combines quantitative metrics with qualitative analyses, allowing users to navigate seamlessly between data visualisations, interpretive texts, and linked resources in the H2IOSC Marketplace. The structure is organised around seven core thematic areas that correspond to the main research and monitoring axes of the project.

The introductory section provides the conceptual and methodological framework of the Observatory, situating it within the H2IOSC and EOSC contexts. Subsequent sections focus on data derived from interviews and focus groups, offering qualitative insights into researchers' experiences, institutional practices, and perceived challenges. Other areas display the results of online surveys, providing aggregated visualisations of responses through charts, tables, and key performance indicators (KPIs). Dedicated subsections highlight the projects analysed within the DHeLO platform, including metadata mappings, methodological descriptions, and identified impacts.

Focus group

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Introduzione

I focus group dell'Osservatorio H2IOSC rappresentano uno strumento qualitativo centrale per comprendere in profondità il punto di vista delle comunità scientifiche, raccogliere esperienze dirette e intercettare bisogni emergenti nel campo delle infrastrutture di ricerca.

Le sessioni sono progettate per stimolare il confronto tra discipline, favorire il dialogo tra ruoli diversi e far emergere anche esigenze latenti, difficilmente rilevabili attraverso metodi puramente quantitativi. I contenuti raccolti vengono analizzati con approccio tematico, sistematizzati e integrati con altri strumenti dell'Osservatorio, come survey, interviste e analisi dei dati d'uso delle infrastrutture.

Lo scopo dei focus group non è solo descrittivo, ma anche propositivo: i risultati concorrono a identificare aree di intervento prioritarie, valorizzare pratiche virtuose e orientare lo sviluppo di soluzioni digitali e infrastrutturali più efficaci. In particolare, questo strumento è strategico per accompagnare l'estensione progressiva di H2IOSC verso nuovi ambiti disciplinari, come le Scienze Sociali e Umanistiche (SSH), e favorire una visione condivisa e realmente partecipata del futuro della ricerca.

Area Focus Group

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Focus group recenti

Attraverso incontri guidati e moderati, ricercatori, docenti, responsabili tecnici, stakeholder istituzionali e rappresentanti di enti partner sono invitati a confrontarsi in modo aperto su pratiche, strumenti, modelli organizzativi e sfide quotidiane che caratterizzano il loro lavoro.

Vedi tutti

Focus Group: infrastrutture di ricerca e SSH: voci, esperienze e desideri per il futuro

Focus Group 09/04/2023

Titolo alternativo: #SegniArcheologia
Start: 2014
End: 2020

Scheda progetto →

Condividi

Focus Group: infrastrutture di ricerca e SSH: voci, esperienze e desideri per il futuro

Focus Group 09/04/2023

ARCH Project: #SegniArcheologia
Start: 2019
End: 2022

Scheda progetto →

Condividi

Focus Group: infrastrutture di ricerca e SSH: voci, esperienze e desideri per il futuro

Focus Group 09/04/2023

Titolo alternativo: IDEHA
Start: 2014
End: ongoing

Scheda progetto →

Condividi

Figure 32: The H2IOSC Observatory section about focus groups

Quali tra queste infrastrutture per le scienze umane e sociali conosci?

Le infrastrutture più note risultano CLARIN (41,2%) e DARIAH (32,8%), seguite da E-RHIS (11,5%) e OPERAS (9,9%). Solo una piccola parte indica "Nessuna" o altre infrastrutture come "OpenEdition" e "CLARIN ERIC"

Fai/hai fatto uso di servizi di una di queste infrastrutture?

La maggioranza degli intervistati si suddivide tra chi ha già avuto esperienze occasionali e chi, pur non avendo ancora partecipato, manifesta apertura e curiosità. L'utilizzo abituale riguarda una quota più ristretta, mentre il disinteresse risulta marginale. Questo quadro suggerisce un potenziale di crescita, soprattutto attraverso iniziative che incentivino la partecipazione e consolidino l'interesse già espresso.

Figure 33: An example of interactive data visualisation from the questionnaires section

A participatory section allows external users to contribute suggestions, request data, or propose collaborations, while a regularly updated news area reports on ongoing activities, publications, and events. This cross-cutting structure is complemented by a navigational model based on dynamic visual components—such as interactive dashboards, linked datasets, and contextual breadcrumbs—that ensure an intuitive and integrated user experience.

8.5 Functionalities and interaction with the H2IOSC Marketplace

The H2IOSC Observatory and the Marketplace operate in continuous synergy, forming two complementary nodes of the same federated infrastructure. The Marketplace provides access to the digital assets of the participating research infrastructures, while the Observatory analyses their use and evolution over time. This integration allows for real-time monitoring of resource ingestion, user behaviour, and service uptake, thus ensuring adaptive management of the H2IOSC ecosystem.

Through the Observatory's dashboard, stakeholders can visualise correlations between community needs, research domains, and the availability of digital tools and datasets. The

system enables the periodic update of information and supports the generation of analytical reports on the progress of FAIRification, interoperability, and community engagement. In this way, the Observatory plays a central role in aligning the digital offer of H2IOSC with the evolving requirements of its user base.

Statistiche dal Marketplace

Marketplace è la piattaforma online che favorisce la scoperta e l'accesso a servizi, strumenti, dataset e altre risorse prodotte dalle Infrastrutture di Ricerca partecipanti.

Vedi tutte

Figure 34: Marketplace-Observatory interaction: statistics about published resources

8.6 Sustainability, adaptability, and long-term vision

One of the Observatory's defining features is its iterative and adaptive nature. Designed as a living system, it is continuously updated through repeated cycles of data collection, validation, and analysis. This iterative process ensures that the Observatory remains responsive to emerging trends, new technologies, and evolving scholarly practices. Over time, it expands into adjacent domains of research and innovation, progressively encompassing a broader spectrum of data-driven and human-centered perspectives.

In line with the Open Science ethos, the Observatory's methodologies, datasets, and analytical instruments are openly documented and, where possible, made reusable by other projects. By offering an evidence-based understanding of how researchers interact with data, tools, and infrastructures, the H2IOSC Observatory contributes to aligning research practices with the digital services provided by the federation, supporting the long-term sustainability and relevance of the H2IOSC ecosystem.

8.7 Current development status

As of October 2025, the technical implementation of H2IOSC Observatory is ongoing, in parallel with the definition of interoperability protocols connecting it to the Marketplace. The conceptual framework, visual design, and information architecture are fully defined, and the main wireframes and UI prototypes are developed.

The development is conducted maintaining strong alignment between conceptual and operational dimensions, thus ensuring that the Observatory evolves into a robust, scalable, and sustainable monitoring infrastructure.

The H2IOSC Observatory embodies the project's commitment to openness, transparency, and continuous improvement. As both an analytical tool and a participatory interface, it bridges the gap between research practices and digital infrastructures, translating data into actionable insights and strategic guidance. Through its integration with the H2IOSC Marketplace, it ensures that the federation remains dynamic, reflective, and responsive to the needs of its communities, consolidating its contribution to the broader European Open Science landscape.

9. Conclusions

Through its analytical and community-oriented actions, WP2 contributes to shaping a sustainable and interoperable ecosystem for Humanities and Cultural Heritage research within H2IOSC.

The coordinated work of CLARIN-IT, DARIAH-IT, E-RIHS.it, and OPERAS-IT within WP2 has laid both the methodological and operational foundations for mapping the national landscape of digital research practices, data, and infrastructures.

By combining quantitative and qualitative approaches—including surveys, interviews, and focus groups—the work has enabled a multi-layered understanding of the needs and expectations of the scholarly communities connected to each research infrastructure. The surveys provided a quantitative overview of existing digital resources, services, and user profiles, highlighting the diversity of disciplinary approaches and the variety of infrastructural practices across domains. The interviews allowed for an in-depth exploration of practices, needs, and expectations. The focus groups further complemented these insights by fostering discussion among representatives from different communities, facilitating consensus building and the identification of shared priorities for future collaboration. Together, these methods have produced an evidence-based and participatory representation of the national research ecosystem—ensuring comparability and a stronger alignment between user perspectives and infrastructure design.

One of the main contributions of this work is the integration of community engagement into the landscape assessment process, making it both an analytical and participatory endeavour. Initiatives such as the “CLARIN Cafés” and “I Giovedì di H2IOSC” have served as participatory platforms that combine dissemination, consultation, and co-design. These activities function as open forums where researchers and infrastructure experts exchange experiences, discuss methodological and technical challenges, and identify priorities and concrete needs related to data management, interoperability, and service use, thus ensuring that infrastructure development remains user-driven and responsive to disciplinary diversity.

The definition of the H2IOSC Permanent Observatory represents a further step toward operational maturity. Conceived as an evolving analytical and participatory environment, the Observatory translates the results of WP2 into a dynamic and continuously updated monitoring system. Its modular design and interoperability with the H2IOSC Marketplace will enable the integration of usage metrics, community feedback, and policy indicators, thereby supporting adaptive governance, FAIR compliance monitoring and long-term sustainability.

Overall, the work accomplished in WP2 has laid the groundwork for a data- and community-driven national infrastructure, capable of evolving in response to emerging needs and policy directions. The integration of landscape and observatory components establishes a methodological backbone for the federation and positions H2IOSC as a reference model for implementing FAIR and Open Science principles across the Humanities and Cultural Heritage domains.

Looking ahead, the results of WP2 will inform the next project phases, supporting the design of new services, training activities, and collaborative frameworks. By embedding user

participation and evidence-based analysis at the core of infrastructure development, H2IOSC is well positioned to act as a living cluster of infrastructures aligned with the evolving European Open Science ecosystem.

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Annex 1: Questionnaire structure and layout

Ciao, grazie per il tuo interesse a partecipare a questa indagine.

Questo questionario è stato sviluppato dal team del **Work Package 2** del progetto PNRR-IR **H2IOSC** – Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>) per **nessità di conoscere meglio e coinvolgere le comunità delle scienze umane, sociali e del patrimonio culturale** individuate come di riferimento per le infrastrutture di ricerca CLARIN, DARIAH, E-RHS e OPERAS.

Il questionario è **rivolto a tutti gli studiosi**: studenti, ricercatori, professori, cultori della materia ed esperti delle discipline sopra indicate.

I **temi** su cui ti chiederemo di dare il tuo personale contributo **saranno** in merito a:

- i) uso e/o creazione di risorse dati, tecnologie, software e servizi nella tua area di ricerca;
- ii) conoscenza delle infrastrutture di ricerca;
- iii) bisogni/desideri di formazione;
- iv) abitudini di pubblicazione.

Per rispondere sono previsti massimo di **10 minuti**. Se vorrai, al termine del questionario, potrai decidere se contribuire ulteriormente a questo lavoro di ricerca rispondendo ad una seconda parte dell'indagine.

Per interrompere la compilazione del questionario e continuare in un secondo momento, basterà cliccare sul tasto "**salva**" in alto a destra. Per riprendere la compilazione sarà necessario accedere **solamente** dal link ricevuto via mail.

Per qualsiasi necessità o dubbio relativamente alla compilazione del questionario è possibile **contattare**:

Monica Monachini WP2 Leader: monica.monachini@ilc.cnr.it

Valeria Quochi WP2: valeria.quochi@ilc.cnr.it

Roberta Bianca Luzietti: robertabianca.luzietti@ilc.cnr.it

Roberta Ottaviani (privacy policy): roberta.ottaviani@ilc.cnr.it

Informativa resa ai sensi dell'art.13 del Regolamento UE n. 2016/679

Gentile rispondente,

desideriamo informarla che il Regolamento UE n. 679/2016 "Regolamento generale sulla protezione dei dati" prevede la tutela delle persone rispetto al trattamento dei dati personali. Secondo la normativa indicata, tale trattamento sarà improntato ai principi di liceità, correttezza e trasparenza, adeguatezza, pertinenza e limitazione, esattezza e aggiornamento, non eccedenza e responsabilizzazione. I dati personali sono trattati, ai sensi dell'art. 6, comma 1 lettera a) del GDPR, previo Suo consenso.

Pertanto, Le forniamo le seguenti informazioni:

1. I dati da Lei forniti appartengono alle seguenti categorie:
 - o Dati anagrafici: nome, cognome (se presenti in indirizzo e-mail), **anno di nascita** (dato raccolto al solo scopo di analisi statistica)
 - o Dati di contatto: **indirizzo e-mail**
 - o Dati relativi alla sua **professione**: livello di carriera, istituto di appartenenza, settore e sottosettore di ricerca

I dati verranno trattati per finalità di ricerca scientifica, nell'ambito del progetto di ricerca Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) www.h2iosc.cnr.it.

Progetto IR0000029 - Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (H2IOSC) - Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Missione 4, "Istruzione e Ricerca" - Componente 2, "Dalla ricerca all'impresa" - Linea di investimento 3.1 del PNRR, Azione 3.1.1 "Creazione di nuove IR o potenziamento di quelle esistenti che concorrono agli obiettivi di Eccellenza Scientifica di Horizon Europe e costituzione di reti" - Area ESFRI S&CI. Finanziato dall'Unione europea - NextGeneration EU (CUP B63C22000730005).

La ricerca è **finalizzata** alla creazione di un cluster federato e inclusivo di infrastrutture di ricerca (IR) all'interno del dominio European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure (ESFRI) riguardo l'innovazione sociale e culturale per consentire ai ricercatori di varie discipline nei settori delle scienze umane, delle tecnologie linguistiche e dei beni culturali di collaborare alla ricerca intensiva di dati e condurre analisi complesse.

Ho letto e compreso il testo dell'informativa

Avanti

Figure 35: introduction and presentation of structure and purpose of the questionnaire together with privacy and policy statement

Prima di procedere

* 1 Come sei venuto/a a conoscenza di questo questionario?

Il commento è permesso solo quando l'opzione relativa è stata scelta.

<input type="checkbox"/> Associazione Italiana Scienze della Voce (AISV)	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Associazione Italiana Linguistica Applicata (AItLA)	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Società Linguistica Italiana (SLI)	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Associazione Italiana Linguistica Computazione (AILC)	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Società Italiana di Glottologia (SIG)	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> Archeologia e Calcolatori	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> CNR-ILC	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> CNR-ISPC	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> CNR-OVI	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> CLARIN-IT	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> CNR-ILIESI	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> DARIAH-IT	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> E-RIHS-IT	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> OPERAS-IT	<input type="text"/>
<input type="checkbox"/> H2IOSC	<input type="text"/>
Altro: <input type="text"/>	<input type="text"/>

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 36: information on how the respondents received the notification to answer the questionnaire

Informazioni personali

*** 2 Posizione/livello di carriera**

<https://www.more-4.eu/indicator-tool/career-stages-r1-to-r4>

Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Studente

Early stage/Junior

Mid-career

Senior

Inserire qui sotto il commento:

*** 3 Dipartimento/istituto di afferenza/ufficio di competenza**

Specificare la propria o le proprie istituzioni di afferenza.

Ad esempio: dipartimento universitario, istituto CNR, ufficio di competenza.

*** 4 Anno di nascita**

Si ricorda che tale informazione verrà impiegata per soli fini statistici, come specificato nell'informativa.

Per questo campo sono consentiti solo valori numerici

Indietro Avanti

Figure 37: personal information

Ambito disciplinare

* 5 Ambito disciplinare

🔍 Indicare uno o più settori e sottosectori disciplinari ERC di riferimento.
📌 Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques
- PE4_11 Physical chemistry of biological systems
- PE5_1 Structural properties of materials
- PE5_3 Surface modification
- PE5_14 Macromolecular chemistry
- PE6_1 Computer architecture, pervasive computing, ubiquitous computing
- PE6_3 Software engineering, operating systems, computer languages
- PE6_4 Theoretical computer science, formal methods, and quantum computing
- PE6_6 Algorithms, distributed, parallel and network algorithms, algorithmic game theory
- PE6_7 Artificial intelligence, intelligent systems, multi agent systems
- PE6_11 Machine learning, statistical data processing and applications using signal processing (e.g. speech, image, video) comparative
- SH4_1 Cognitive basis of human development and education, developmental disorders; comparative cognition
- SH4_8 Language learning and processing (first and second languages)
- SH4_9 Theoretical linguistics; computational linguistics
- SH4_10 Language typology; historical linguistics
- SH4_11 Pragmatics, sociolinguistics, linguistic anthropology, discourse analysis
- SH5_1 Classics, ancient literature and art
- SH5_2 Theory and history of literature, comparative literature
- SH5_3 Philology and palaeography
- SH5_8 Cultural studies, cultural identities and memories, cultural heritage
- SH5_12 Computational modelling and digitisation in the cultural sphere
- SH6_1 Historiography, theory and methods in history, including the analysis of digital data
- SH6_2 Classical archaeology, history of archaeology
- SH6_3 General archaeology, archaeometry, landscape archaeology
- Altro:

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 38: information on the disciplinary sector of respondents (ERC)

Utilizzo e creazione di risorse dati, tecnologie, software e servizi

*⁶ Nel corso delle proprie ricerche/studi, è stata maturata **esperienza di utilizzo** di risorse dati, tecnologie digitali e/o servizi? Se sì, quali?

📌 Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- GIS / Dataset geografici
- Rilievo 2D / 3D - rilievo fotogrammetrico, laser scanning, plano-altimetrico (georiferito o non)
- Dataset di analisi - diagnostiche, prospezioni geofisiche
- Database relazionali - inventari, cataloghi, database di reperti
- Prodotto multimediale / virtuale - video, dataset fotografici, ricostruzioni virtuali, ambienti virtuali
- Banca dati linguistici
- Wordnet
- Piattaforma per fruizione di un servizio specifico
- Corpus di lingua parlata
- Corpus di lingua scritta
- Corpus multimodale
- Archivio
- Tokenizer
- Software per annotazione
- Non ho usato nulla
- Altro:

Figure 39: information on experience in using data resources, tools and services

* 7 Nel corso delle proprie ricerche/studi, è stata maturata **esperienza nella creazione** di risorse dati, tecnologie digitali e/o servizi?

Se sì, quali?

📌 Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- GIS / Dataset geografici
- Rilievo 2D / 3D - rilievo fotogrammetrico, laser scanning, plano-altimetrico (georiferito o non)
- Dataset di analisi - diagnostiche, prospezioni geofisiche
- Database relazionali - inventari, cataloghi, database di reperti
- Prodotto multimediale / virtuale - video, dataset fotografici, ricostruzioni virtuali, ambienti virtuali
- Banca dati linguistici
- Wordnet
- Piattaforma per fruizione di un servizio specifico
- Corpus di lingua parlata
- Corpus di lingua scritta
- Corpus multimodale
- Archivio
- Tokenizer
- Software per annotazione
- Non ho creato nulla
- Altro:

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 40: information on experience in creating data resources, tools and services

Conoscenza delle infrastrutture di ricerca

* 8 Conosci le infrastrutture di ricerca?

! Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

- Sì
 No

* 9 Quali tra queste infrastrutture per le scienze umane e sociali conosci?

! Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- CLARIN
 DARIAH
 E-RIHS
 OPERAS
 Nessuna
 Altro:

* 10 Fai/hai fatto uso di servizi di una di queste infrastrutture?

! Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

- Sì, abitualmente
 Sì, occasionalmente
 No, ma vorrei saperne di più
 No, non sono interessato/a

* 12 Cosa ti aspetti che le infrastrutture di ricerca offrano alla tua comunità in termini di risorse, tecnologie, servizi ecc.?

! In alternativa, indicare "non so"

OR

Conoscenza delle infrastrutture di ricerca

* 8 Conosci le infrastrutture di ricerca?

📌 Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Sì

No

Indietro Avanti

Figure 41: information on the (level of) knowledge of Research Infrastructures (in general)

H2IOSC

* 15 Conoscevi il progetto H2IOSC prima di questo questionario?

📌 Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Sì

No

16 Sei coinvolta/o in un progetto PNRR, quale ad esempio un Partenariato Esteso o altri interventi?

📌 Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Sì

No

17 Se sì, indicare quale (nel caso di Partenariato Esteso indica anche lo Spoke di riferimento)

18 Se sì, sai se sono già state avviate collaborazioni tra il partenariato/intervento di cui fai parte ed H2IOSC?

Figure 42: information on the (level of) knowledge of the H²IOSC project

Formazione

* 15 Su quali temi saresti interessato/a a ricevere formazione e/o ritieni prioritari?

! Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- Licenze d'uso
- Principi FAIR
- Deposito di risorse/tecnologie/servizi in un repository
- Accesso ad archivi, repository, database ecc.
- Strumenti per l'analisi dei dati
- Modelli e formati standard di rappresentazione dei dati
- Buone pratiche per la gestione e conservazione dei dati
- Accesso e riuso di materiali di training già esistenti
- Scienza aperta
- Pubblicare open access e open source
- Altro:

* 16 Con quale modalità?

! Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- A distanza e self-paced
- A distanza e live
- In presenza
- Altro:

Indietro Avanti

Figure 43: information on training preferences

Pubblicazioni

* 17 Quale sistema di pubblicazione utilizza la propria istituzione di appartenenza?

📌 Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- Open Journals System (OJS)
- Open Monograph Press (OMP)
- Lodel
- DSpace
- Dataverse
- Janeway
- Pressbooks
- WordPress
- Drupal
- PubPub
- Manifold
- BrenchPress
- Editorial manager
- Scholar online
- Non so
- Altro:

* 18 Che tipo di pubblicazioni vengono fatte in open access dalla propria istituzione di appartenenza?

📌 Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- Riviste scientifiche
- Monografie scientifiche
- Curatele
- Atti di convegno
- Letteratura grigia
- Pubblicazioni multimediali (video, installazioni ...)
- Dataset
- Software
- Pubblicazioni non accademiche
- Non so
- Altro:

* 19 Che tipo di licenze usi maggiormente?

📌 Scegliere una o più delle seguenti opzioni

- CC BY
- CC BY-SA
- CC BY-NC
- CC BY-SA-NC
- CC BY-ND
- CC BY-NC-ND
- CC0
- Apache
- GPL 3.0
- Nessuna
- Altro:

[Indietro](#) [Avanti](#)

Figure 44: information on publication practices

Informazioni di contatto

* 20 Caro/a rispondente, arrivati a questo punto, il questionario prevede un secondo form (massimo **15 minuti**) dedicato alla raccolta di alcune informazioni in merito all'uso e creazione di risorse dati, tecnologie, software e servizi.
Per darti maggiore flessibilità, ti chiediamo come preferiresti procedere.

📌 Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Intervista guidata

Questionario online

Non voglio continuare

* 21 Consenso all'utilizzo dell'indirizzo e-mail per ragioni di contatto e/o richieste di partecipazione ad altre attività del progetto.

📌 Questo è il testo di help della domanda.

📌 Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

Acconsento all'utilizzo dell'indirizzo e-mail per ragioni di contatto e/o richieste di partecipazione ad altre attività del progetto.

Non acconsento all'utilizzo dell'indirizzo e-mail per ragioni di contatto e/o richieste di partecipazione ad altre attività del progetto.

* 22 Per favore, fornire un indirizzo e-mail valido

📌 Si ricorda che l'indirizzo e-mail verrà impiegato per soli fini di ricerca, come indicato nell'informativa. Eventuali informazioni di nome e cognome presenti nell'indirizzo e-mail verranno separate dalle risposte del questionario (esaminate in modo aggregato) poiché escluse dall'analisi dei dati.

mail.com

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 45: contact information

OR

Informazioni di contatto

* 20 Caro/a rispondente, arrivati a questo punto, il questionario prevede un secondo form (massimo **15 minuti**) dedicato alla raccolta di alcune informazioni in merito all'uso e creazione di risorse dati, tecnologie, software e servizi.

Per darti maggiore flessibilità, ti chiediamo come preferiresti procedere.

📌 Scegliere solo una delle seguenti voci

- Intervista guidata
- Questionario online
- Non voglio continuare

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 46: information on how to proceed with the second questionnaire

Fine

* 23 Grazie per aver compilato il questionario! La seconda parte di indagine è disponibile qui: [link]

Qualora siano state riscontrate difficoltà durante la compilazione o si vogliano fornire osservazioni e/o suggerimenti, lasciare un commento qui di seguito.

Indietro

Invia

Work Package 2 - Progetto PNRR-IR **H2IOSC** – Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>)
[Stampare le risposte.](#)

Figure 47: final comments section

Avanzato

Ciao, grazie per il tuo interesse a proseguire con l'indagine.

Questa seconda parte prevede la raccolta di alcune informazioni di base in merito all'uso e creazione di risorse dati, tecnologie, software e servizi.

Il questionario può durare al **massimo 15 minuti** ed è composto da **4 sezioni** (risorse create, risorse usate, tecnologie create e tecnologie usate). Se ri-tieni di non poter rispondere a una delle sezioni (ad esempio, perché non hai creato risorse) potrai passare direttamente alla sezione successiva.

Anche in questo caso, **per interrompere la compilazione** del questionario e continuare in un secondo momento, basterà cliccare sul tasto "**salva**" in alto a destra. Per riprendere la compilazione sarà necessario accedere **solamente** dal link ricevuto via mail.

Per qualsiasi necessità o dubbio relativamente alla compilazione del questionario è possibile **contattare**:

Monica Monachini WP2 Leader: monica.monachini@ilc.cnr.it

Valeria Quochi WP2: valeria.quochi@ilc.cnr.it

Roberta Bianca Luzietti: robertabianca.luzietti@ilc.cnr.it

Avanti

Figure 48: introductory information on the structure, purpose and time required to answer the questionnaire

Prima di procedere

Per ulteriori informazioni relative al trattamento dei dati al fine di tutela della privacy contattare roberta.ottaviani@ilc.cnr.it e monica.monachini@ilc.cnr.it

*¹ A scopo di riconciliazione con le risposte del precedente questionario compilato, **fornire nuovamente lo stesso indirizzo e-mail.**

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 49: e-mail request to match responses in previous questionnaire

Risorse dati create

- ➔ Se nel corso della tua carriera **non hai creato** risorse dati, puoi passare alla sezione successiva cliccando sul tasto "**avanti**" in basso a destra.
- ➔ Se **cambi idea**, puoi tornare "**indietro**" e compilare le risposte in qualsiasi momento.
- ➔ Per **interrompere la compilazione** del questionario e riprendere in un secondo momento **salvando le risposte**, clicca sul tasto "**salva**" in alto a destra. Potrai accedere all'indagine **solamente** dal link ricevuto via mail.

3 Indica **5 risorse dati che hai creato** (o hai contribuito a creare) nel corso della tua carriera.

1

+ Aggiungi riga

4 Fornisci, per favore, le seguenti **informazioni**:

- **Tipologia**: Database, Lessico, Corpus lingua scritta/parlata, Corpus multimodale, Modello 3D, Archivio sonoro, Video, ecc.
- **Formato**: XML, XML TEI, CONLL-U, Oracle, SQL, JPEG, RAW, CSV, WAV, Mp4, OBJ, EFX, ecc.
- **PID/DOI/Handle**: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/persistent-identifiers>
- **Licenza**: CC-BY, CC-BY-NC, CC BY-SA, CC BY-SA-NC, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND, CC0, ecc.
- **Stato**: Nuova creazione, aggiornamento di una versione precedente, ecc.
- **Accessibile da**: Computer personale/di laboratorio, repository certificato, repository online (es. Zenodo), ecc.
- **Nessuna risposta**: NA

	Tipologia	Formato	PID/DOI /Handle	Licenza	Stato	Accessibile da
hello	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					

5 Con quali **finalità** hai creato queste risorse dati?

	Scopo
hello	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="text"/>

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 50: information regarding data resources created

Risorse dati usate

- ➔ Se nel corso della tua carriera **non hai usato** risorse dati, puoi passare alla sezione successiva cliccando sul tasto "**avanti**" in basso a destra.
- ➔ Se **cambi idea**, puoi tornare "**indietro**" e compilare le risposte in qualsiasi momento.
- ➔ Per **interrompere la compilazione** del questionario e riprendere in un secondo momento **salvando le risposte**, clicca sul tasto "**salva**" in alto a destra. Potrai accedere all'indagine **solamente** dal link ricevuto via mail.

6 Indica le **5 risorse dati che usi di più** (perché più frequenti o più importanti) per le tue ricerche.

1

+ Aggiungi riga

7 Fornisci, per favore, le seguenti **informazioni**:

- **Tipologia**: Database, Lessico, Corpus lingua scritta/parlata, Corpus multimodale, Modello 3D, Archivio sonoro, Video, ecc.
- **Formato**: XML, XML TEI, CONLL-U, Oracle, SQL, JPEG, RAW, CSV, WAV, Mp4, OBJ, EFX, ecc.
- **PID/DOI/Handle**: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/persistent-identifiers>
- **Licenza**: CC-BY, CC-BY-NC, CC BY-SA, CC BY-SA-NC, CC BY-ND, CC BY-NC-ND, CC0, ecc.
- **Stato**: Nuova creazione, aggiornamento di una versione precedente
- **Accessibile da**: Computer personale/di laboratorio, repository certificato, repository online (es. Zenodo), ecc.
- **Nessuna risposta**: NA

	Tipologia	Formato	PID/DOI /Handle	Licenza	Stato	Accessibile da
helloooo	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					

8 Con quali **finalità** usi/hai usato queste risorse?

	Scopo
helloooo	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="text"/>

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 51: information regarding data resources used

Tecnologie, software e servizi creati

- ➔ Se nel corso della tua carriera **non hai creato** tecnologie, software o servizi, puoi passare alla sezione successiva cliccando sul tasto **"avanti"** in basso a destra.
- ➔ Se **cambi idea**, puoi tornare **"indietro"** e compilare le risposte in qualsiasi momento.
- ➔ Per **interrompere la compilazione** del questionario e riprendere in un secondo momento **salvando le risposte**, clicca sul tasto **"salva"** in alto a destra. Potrai accedere all'indagine **solamente** dal link ricevuto via mail.

9 Indica **5 tecnologie, software o servizi che hai creato** (o hai contribuito a creare) nel corso della tua carriera.

1

+ Aggiungi riga

10 Fornisci, per favore, le seguenti **informazioni**:

- **Tipologia**: Tokenizer, Query handler, Software per applicazioni 3D, Servizio di annotazione automatica, ecc.
- **Formato**: Python, Java, SQL, C++, OBJ, FBX, ecc.
- **PID/DOI/Handle**: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/persistent-identifiers>
- **Licenza**: CC-BY, CC-BY-SA, CC-BY-NC, CC-BY-NC-SA, CC0, Apache, GPL 3.0, ecc.
- **Stato**: Nuova creazione, aggiornamento di una versione precedente, ecc.
- **Accessibile da**: Computer personale/di laboratorio, repository certificato, repository online (es. Zenodo, GitHub), ecc.
- **Nessuna risposta**: NA

	Tipologia	Formato	PID/DOI /Handle	Licenza	Stato	Accessibile da
hello!	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					

11 Con quali **finalità** hai creato queste risorse dati?

	Scopo
hello!	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="text"/>

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 52: information regarding tools and software created

Tecnologie, software e servizi usati

- ➔ Se nel corso della tua carriera **non hai usato** tecnologie, software o servizi, puoi passare alla sezione successiva cliccando sul tasto **"avanti"** in basso a destra.
- ➔ Se **cambi idea**, puoi tornare **"indietro"** e compilare le risposte in qualsiasi momento.
- ➔ Per **interrompere la compilazione** del questionario e riprendere in un secondo momento **salvando le risposte**, clicca sul tasto **"salva"** in alto a destra. Potrai accedere all'indagine **solamente** dal link ricevuto via mail.

12 Indica **5 tecnologie, software, o servizi che usi di più** (perché più frequenti o più importanti) per le tue ricerche.

1

+ Aggiungi riga

13 Fornisci, per favore, le seguenti **informazioni**:

- **Tipologia**: Tokenizer, Query handler, Software per applicazioni 3D, Servizio di annotazione automatica, ecc.
- **Formato**: Python, Java, SQL, C++, OBJ, FBX, ecc.
- **PID/DOI/Handle**: <https://www.clarin.eu/content/persistent-identifiers>
- **Licenza**: CC-BY, CC-BY-SA, CC-BY-NC, CC-BY-NC-SA, CC0, Apache, GPL 3.0, ecc.
- **Stato**: Nuova creazione, aggiornamento di una versione precedente, ecc.
- **Accessibile da**: Computer personale/di laboratorio, repository certificato, repository online (es. Zenodo, GitHub), ecc.
- **Nessuna risposta**: NA

	Tipologia	Formato	PID/DOI/Handle	Licenza	Stato	Accessibile da
we we	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					
	<input type="text"/>					

14 Con quali **finalità** usi/hai usato queste tecnologie?

	Scopo
we we	<input type="text"/>
	<input type="text"/>

Indietro

Avanti

Figure 53: information regarding tools and software used

Conclusione

* 50 Grazie per aver compilato il questionario!
Qualora siano state riscontrate difficoltà durante la compilazione del questionario oppure ci sono altre osservazioni e/o suggerimenti, lasciare un commento qui di seguito.

Indietro

Avanti

Work Package 2 - Progetto PNRR-IR **H2IOSC** – Humanities and Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud (<https://www.h2iosc.cnr.it/>)
[Stampare le risposte.](#)

Figure 54: final comments section

Annex 2: Focus groups preparation materials

29 luglio 2024 | 26 marzo 2025.

Nuovo incontro per ricercatrici e ricercatori: Mid-Career, Senior.

I partecipanti devono essere:

- persone aperte ed estroverse;
- studiosi **fortemente orientati al futuro**;
- dai solidi studi in SSH sia “classico” che “innovativo”;
- studiosi anche critici ma in termini costruttivi i verso il futuro digitale delle SSH.

Il gruppo deve, in fine, rispondere alle caratteristiche di età, posizione nella professione e genere, individuate dalla tabella qui di seguito.

Età in anni compiuti	Donne		Uomini	
	Assegniste senior	Ricercatrici senior/Professori universitari	Assegnisti senior	Ricercatori senior/Professori universitari
33-40				
41 ed oltre				

Ogni infrastruttura individua 2 partecipanti. La selezione avviene per conoscenza diretta.

Gli studiosi individuati **non** devono essere inseriti in attività del progetto H2IOSC.

16 dicembre 2024 | 27 marzo 2025

Studenti, early stage/junior researchers:

I partecipanti devono essere:

- persone aperte ed estroverse;
- studenti o giovani ricercatori **fortemente orientati al futuro**;
- studenti o giovani ricercatori anche critici ma in termini costruttivi i verso il futuro digitale delle SSH.

Il gruppo deve, in fine, rispondere alle caratteristiche di età, posizione nella professione e genere, individuate dalla tabella qui di seguito.

Età in anni compiuti	Donne		Uomini	
	Dottorandi	Post-doc/Assegnisti di ricerca/junior researcher	Dottorandi	Post-doc/Assegnisti di ricerca/junior researcher
25 - 28				
29 - 32				

Ogni infrastruttura individua 2 partecipanti. La selezione avviene per conoscenza diretta.

Gli studenti/assegnisti individuati **non** devono essere inseriti in attività del progetto H2IOSC.

- Per i soli dottorandi, anche non afferenti agli istituti ma afferenti a dipartimenti universitari strettamente collegati agli istituti attraverso accordi formalmente riconosciuti.
- I dottorandi possono anche essere iscritti ad associazioni che costituiscono le comunità di riferimento per gli Istituti CNR (es. dottorandi iscritti ad AIUCD);

Differenze tra “Assegnisti di ricerca/junior” e “Assegnisti senior” risiede nel numero di anni di assegno. I primi hanno da uno a due anni di esperienza i secondi tre e più anni come assegnisti di ricerca.

Form with selection criteria for focus group participants.

Gentilissime, Gentilissimi,

grazie per la vostra disponibilità ed il tempo che ci dedicherete.

- Vi confermo che l'incontro si terrà il *29 luglio prossimo*.

L'incontro, come già sapete, è un momento di confronto tra *esperti delle SSH* sul tema delle risorse, degli gli strumenti e dei servizi che un'infrastruttura cloud di ricerca potrà offrire in un *prossimo futuro*.

Ognuno potrà *esprimere il proprio parere liberamente*, non ci saranno risposte giuste o sbagliate e ogni opinione, idea o posizione sarà importante ai fini della discussione.

Non sono previste competenze specifiche, oltre a quelle già possedute e ogni intervento sarà importante per il buon esito dell'incontro.

Ci incontreremo on-line alle 10,00. Oltre a voi esperti saremo presenti io e la collega Marta Caradonna.

Abbiamo previsto un tempo massimo di 2 ore che potremmo non occupare interamente se trattati tutti gli argomenti e data l'opportunità a tutti i convenuti di confrontarsi, si spendesse meno tempo di quello previsto.

Seguirà a questa una seconda comunicazione contenente file di utilità e il consenso alla privacy.

- Prima di salutarvi ricordo che **la discussione sarà registrata e trascritta automaticamente**, questo ci consentirà il **riascolto a scopi conoscitivi**. *Il trattamento dei dati sarà rigorosamente anonimo.*

Un caro saluto a tutte e tutti.

A presto sentirci.

Nicola

Focus group invitation e-mail

1. Anno di nascita: _____
2. Sesso:
 - a. Preferisco non indicare
 - b. Donna
 - c. Uomo
3. Titolo di Studio: _____
4. Istituto CNR di Afferenza: _____
5. Tipo di contratto:
 - a. TD
 - i. Ricercatore/tecnologo
 - ii. CTER
 - iii. Altro (specificare) _____
 - b. TI
 - i. Ricercatore/tecnologo
 - ii. CTER
 - iii. Altro (specificare) _____
 - c. Altro (specificare): _____
6. Ambiti di ricerca/specializzazioni _____

Form for recording the demographic and professional characteristics of guests

INFORMATIVA PER IL TRATTAMENTO DEI DATI NELL'AMBITO DI UN PROGETTO DI RICERCA ai sensi degli artt. 13 e 14 del Regolamento UE n. 679/2016 del 27.04.2016 "Regolamento generale sulla protezione dei dati" (di seguito "Regolamento") e del D.Lgs. n. 196/2003 "Codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali", come modificato dal D.Lgs. n. 101 del 10.08.2018, recante disposizioni per l'adeguamento dell'ordinamento nazionale al Regolamento europeo.

La informiamo che:

- 1) I suoi dati personali verranno trattati per le seguenti finalità: svolgimento di un incontro di gruppo di esperti. L'incontro rappresenta una delle fasi di ricerca inserita nel progetto H2IOSC Project - Humanities and cultural Heritage Italian Open Science Cloud funded by the European Union – NextGenerationEU – NRRP M4C2 - Project code IR0000029 - CUP B63C22000730005. Nell'ambito di questo progetto il WP2 (Work Package 2) si occupa del "Landscaping and building communities". L'incontro s'inserisce nelle attività di Landscaping. I dati saranno trattati per il tempo necessario dell'analisi e report interno e per l'Unione Europea e, successivamente alla chiusura del progetto, per l'eventuale adempimento di obblighi di legge in conformità alle norme vigenti sulla conservazione degli atti amministrativi.
- 2) I dati personali necessari alla finalità della ricerca sono:
 - Personali comuni: (es. nome/cognome, attività lavorativa, etc.);
- 3) Per ragioni strettamente legate alle finalità di ricerca, il trattamento potrà avere ad oggetto le Sue immagini (fotografie, riprese video, riprese audio-video, radiografie o immagini strumentali, ecc.) o altri dati strumentali. Il trattamento di tali immagini avverrà nel rispetto delle disposizioni di legge, garantendo in tutti i casi in cui ciò sia possibile, il Suo anonimato tramite l'oscuramento dei tratti somatici. Nell'ipotesi in cui il suddetto trattamento sarà necessario, Le sarà richiesto uno specifico consenso, anche ai sensi delle disposizioni di legge sul diritto d'autore, considerato che, sia pure in casi particolari, alcune immagini relative a persone il cui viso è stato oscurato possono consentirne l'identificazione.
- 4) I dati verranno trattati in forma digitale ed analogica, con modalità di organizzazione ed elaborazione correlate alle finalità sopra indicate e, comunque, in modo *da garantirne la sicurezza e la riservatezza*.
- 5) Possono venire a conoscenza dei dati in questione, per il conseguimento delle finalità sopra indicate, il Direttore/Dirigente del Progetto H2IOSC che ha la responsabilità scientifica di H2IOSC, il responsabile del WP2, i componenti del gruppo di ricerca che si occupa del "Landscaping and building communities".
- 6) Il Titolare del trattamento è: il Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Piazzale Aldo Moro n. 7 – 00185 Roma PEC: protocollo-ammcen@pec.cnr.it.
- 7) I dati di contatto del Responsabile della protezione dei dati sono: E-mail: rpd@cnr.it; PEC: protocollo-ammcen@pec.cnr.it presso il Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche – Piazzale Aldo Moro n. 7 – 00185 Roma.
- 8) Al termine della ricerca, nei limiti pertinenti le finalità sopra indicate, i dati dei partecipanti potranno essere comunicati a soggetti terzi, in conformità agli obblighi previsti da leggi, regolamenti, normativa nazionale e comunitaria, nonché da disposizioni impartite da autorità a ciò legittimate da organi di vigilanza e di controllo, ai sensi dell'art. 6 del Reg.UE 2016/679.
- 9) In qualità di interessato, il partecipante ha il diritto di chiedere al Titolare l'accesso ai dati personali che lo riguardano nonché di esercitare i diritti di cui agli articoli 15 e seguenti del Regolamento (UE) 2016/679, tra cui richiedere la rettifica o la cancellazione degli stessi o la limitazione del trattamento o di opporsi al trattamento presentando apposita istanza al contatto di cui al precedente punto 5.

- 10) In qualità di interessato, ricorrendone i presupposti, il partecipante può presentare reclamo al Garante per la protezione dei dati personali quale autorità di controllo secondo le procedure previste.

Acquisizione del consenso dell'interessato

Il/La sottoscritto/a, _____

DICHIARA

di avere letto attentamente e compreso "l'informativa per il trattamento dei dati nell'ambito di un progetto di ricerca ai sensi degli artt. 13 e 14 del Regolamento UE n. 679/2016" ed essere stato informato su:

1. Le finalità e le modalità di trattamento cui sono destinati i dati;
2. la natura dei dati personali conferiti;
3. il tempo di conservazione dei dati così come previsto dalla normativa e la cancellazione degli stessi;
4. i soggetti ai quali i dati personali possono essere comunicati o che possono venirne a conoscenza;
5. i diritti dell'interessato e le relative modalità di esercizio;
6. la possibilità di proporre reclamo al Garante per la Protezione dei dati personali

ESPRIME IL CONSENSO

affinché Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche di Roma tratti i propri dati personali per le finalità e le modalità descritte nell'informativa.

NEGA IL PROPRIO CONSENSO

A che Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche di Roma tratti i propri dati personali per le finalità e le modalità descritte nell'informativa.

Ai fini dell'acquisizione da parte dell'interessato del consenso specifico per il trattamento delle categorie particolari di dati personali, ex art. 9 GDPR,

DICHIARA

di aver ricevuto e preso attenta visione del documento "Informazioni in merito alla partecipazione allo studio";

- di avere avuto la possibilità di fare domande sulla ricerca e di avere ricevuto risposte esaurienti;
- di essere a conoscenza che la partecipazione a questo progetto include la raccolta di informazioni mediante i seguenti strumenti:
 - video-call
 - scheda di rilevazione dati

Ai sensi delle disposizioni del Regolamento (UE) 2016/679 e del D. Lgs. 196/2003 ss.mm.ii., lette le "Informazioni sul trattamento dei dati personali, particolari e genetici" sopra riportate, il/la sottoscritto/a (selezionare quelle pertinenti):

Acconsente Non acconsente

al trattamento dei propri dati NECESSARIO ai fini della partecipazione allo studio di cui trattasi e al suo svolgimento per le finalità sottese;

Acconsente Non acconsente

che le informazioni fornite saranno usate per report, pubblicazioni, siti web (immagini), usando gli stessi termini adoperati nel foglio informativo.

Le informazioni personali raccolte sull'interessato che possono essere identificative (es. nome, residenza...) non saranno condivise al di fuori del gruppo di ricerca;

Acconsente Non acconsente

L'interessato/a è consapevole che i dati saranno depositati con le seguenti modalità: mediante trascrizione anonima, audioregistrazione, database di ricerca, etc;

L'interessato/a è consapevole che l'archiviazione dei dati sarà resa anonima in tal modo eliminando ogni riferimento che possa far identificare la persona.

Luogo e data _____/_____/_____

Firma

Privacy policy format and format for obtaining informed consent to the processing of personal data

uso e/o costruzione di strumenti e/o risorse digitali

- GIS / Dataset geografici
- Rilievo 2D / 3D - rilievo fotogrammetrico, laser scanning, plano-altimetrico (georiferito o non)
- Dataset di analisi - diagnostiche, prospezioni geofisiche
- Database relazionali - inventari, cataloghi, database di reperti
- Prodotto multimediale / virtuale - video, dataset fotografici, ricostruzioni virtuali, ambienti virtuali
- Banca dati linguistici
- Wordnet
- Piattaforma per fruizione di un servizio specifico
- Corpus di lingua parlata
- Corpus di lingua scritta
- Corpus multimodale
- Archivio
- Tokenizer
- Software per annotazione
- Altro tipo di risorsa

List of digital tools and resources used or created, as indicated in question 7 of the first part of the questionnaire

Privacy e registrazione

INFORMATIVA PER IL TRATTAMENTO DEI DATI NELL'AMBITO DI UN PROGETTO DI RICERCA

- ai sensi degli artt. 13 e 14 del Regolamento UE n. 679/2016 del 27.04.2016 "Regolamento generale sulla protezione dei dati" (di seguito "Regolamento") e del D.Lgs. n. 196/2003 "Codice in materia di protezione dei dati personali", come modificato dal D.Lgs. n. 101 del 10.08.2018, recante disposizioni per l'adeguamento dell'ordinamento nazionale al Regolamento europeo.

Incontro video registrato tramite TEAMS

- utilizzato solo per finalità di ricerca ed in modo anonimo, come già indicato nell'informativa inviata via e-mail.

La partecipazione

- implica l'autorizzazione al trattamento dei dati personali compresa la registrazione audio video.

Norme dell'incontro

Il mio ruolo

- è quello di favorire la discussione di gruppo e non quello di interagire singolarmente.

Il ruolo di Marta

- è quello di osservare le interazioni ed intervenire per ridefinire, reindirizzare e migliorare la discussione.

E' auspicabile intervenire uno alla volta prenotando con l'«alzata di mano»

E' consigliabile l'uso della chat

- durante gli interventi o per fissare una domanda/pensiero.

Ogni intervento

- deve svolgersi nell'arco di 2/3 minuti.

Su tutti gli argomenti proposti

- è auspicabile l'intervento di tutti

I temi

- **Uso di risorse, strumenti o servizi digitali per le proprie ricerche negli ultimi 5 anni**
- **Conoscenza di infrastrutture specifiche ed uso delle risorse, degli strumenti e dei servizi di queste**
- **Futuro nel web dei propri ambiti di studio e delle proprie attività di ricerca**
- **Dati FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable e Reusable)**
- **Formazione all'uso delle infrastrutture digitali di ricerca**
- **Eventuali fee o costi delle risorse e degli strumenti digitali**

uso e/o costruzione di strumenti e/o risorse digitali

- GIS / Dataset geografici
- Rilievo 2D / 3D - rilievo fotogrammetrico, laser scanning, plano-altimetrico (georiferito o non)
- Dataset di analisi - diagnostiche, prospezioni geofisiche
- Database relazionali - inventari, cataloghi, database di reperti
- Prodotto multimediale / virtuale - video, dataset fotografici, ricostruzioni virtuali, ambienti virtuali
- Banca dati linguistici
- Wordnet
- Piattaforma per fruizione di un servizio specifico
- Corpus di lingua parlata
- Corpus di lingua scritta
- Corpus multimodale
- Archivio
- Tokenizer
- Software per annotazione

Altro (specificare)

Infrastruttura di ricerca

"infrastrutture di ricerca", **strutture, risorse e servizi** che sono usati dalle comunità di ricerca per condurre ricerca e promuovere l'innovazione nei rispettivi settori. Se del caso, esse possono essere utilizzate al di là della ricerca, ad esempio per **scopi educativi** o di **servizio pubblico**. Esse comprendono: **attrezzature scientifiche** di primaria importanza o serie di strumenti, **risorse** basate sulla conoscenza quali **collezioni, archivi o dati scientifici**, infrastrutture in rete quali **sistemi di dati e calcolo** e **reti di comunicazione** e qualsiasi altra **infrastruttura** di natura **unica** essenziale per raggiungere **l'eccellenza nella ricerca e nell'innovazione**. Tali infrastrutture possono essere "ubicate in un **unico sito**", "**virtuali**" o "**distribuite**"

Dati FAIR

"**Findable, Accessible, Interoperable e Reusable** - in italiano **trovabili, accessibili, interoperabili, riutilizzabili**: sono i requisiti che i dati e i risultati della ricerca dovrebbero avere per aderire al modello della **scienza aperta**, in modo che questi dati siano rintracciabili all'interno della produzione scientifica e possano agevolare il riuso, quando possibile, nella produzione di nuova conoscenza"

Annex 3: DHeLO Metadata

A3.1 DHeLO 1.0 Metadata List

Product table

Field	Explanation
id	Unique identifier of the product
title	Title of the digital product or resource
description	Short description of the content or purpose
category	General category (e.g., dataset, publication, software)
subjectField	Primary disciplinary field
dataProvider	Entity or project that provided the original data
intermediateDataProvider	Entity that transformed or curated the data before final publication
isShownAt	URL of a landing page or metadata record
isShownBy	Direct link to the actual digital resource (e.g., image, dataset)
project	Reference to the associated project
doi	Digital Object Identifier, if available
resourceTypeTools	Type of tool or format used to create or deliver the resource
temporalCoverages	Time periods covered by the content
spatialCoverages	Geographic coverage of the content
ercSector	Corresponding ERC scientific sector
contributors	People or entities who contributed to the product
creators	Main authors or creators of the product

Project table

id	Unique project identifier
title	Project title
alternateTitle	Alternative or short title
founder	Funding body or founding institution
description	Project description or abstract
temporalCoverageStart	Start date of the project
temporalCoverageEnd	End date of the project
website	URL of the project website
coordinators	Main coordinators or principal investigators
participants	Additional team members or collaborating entities
ercSector	Related ERC scientific sector

People table

id	Unique identifier for the person
surname	Last name
name	First name
email	Contact email address
institution	Affiliated institution or organization
nationality	Nationality of the person
position	Academic or professional role (e.g., researcher, curator)

orcidId | ORCID identifier for the person

Institution table

id	Unique identifier for the institution
name	Full institutional name
department	Department or subdivision, if applicable
website	Official website
description	Short institutional description

Tools table

id	Unique tool identifier
name	Tool name
alternateName	Other names or acronyms
type	Tool type (e.g., software, service, library)
isPartOf	Larger software suite or environment the tool belongs to
license	Usage license (e.g., GPL, CC BY)
softwarehouse	Developer or institution responsible for the tool
isShownAt	Landing page for the tool
developers	People or institutions involved in development

A3.2 DHeLO 2.0 Metadata List

FOAF:ORGANIZATION

DCTERMS:TITLE	The official name of the organization, ensuring standardized identification.
DCTERMS:ALTERNATIVETITLE	Any alternative names or abbreviations commonly used for the institution.
DCTERMS:DESCRIPTION	A brief overview of the organization, including research focus and contributions to CH.
DCTERMS:ISPARTOF	Indicates if the organization is part of a larger entity (e.g., a university or research center).
DCTERMS:IDENTIFIER	Unique identifier for the organization (preferably from ROR) for interoperability.
FOAF:HOMEPAGE	URL linking to the organization's official website.

FOAF:PERSON

DCTERMS:TITLE	Full name of the person (given name + surname).
FOAF:NAME	Given name of the person.
FOAF:SURNAME	Surname of the person.
DCTERMS:IDENTIFIER	ORCID identifier linking the person to global research infrastructure.

FOAF:PROJECT

DCTERMS:TITLE	Official title of the project.
DCTERMS:ALTERNATIVETITLE	Alternative names, acronyms, or abbreviations.
DCTERMS:DESCRIPTION	Overview of objectives, methods, and expected impact.
DCTERMS:DATE	Timeframe of the project (start and end dates).
BIBO:STATUS	Current status (e.g., ongoing, completed).

DCTERMS:REPLACES	Links to a previous project that this one continues or replaces.
DCTERMS:ISREPLACEDBY	Refers to a subsequent project that continues or extends this one.
DCTERMS:ISPARTOF	Indicates whether the project is part of a broader framework, such as a consortium or research program.
FOAF:HOMEPAGE	URL of the project's official website.
DCTERMS:IDENTIFIER	DCTERMS: DATASETter for the project (can be internal or from external repositories).
DCTERMS:CREATOR	Coordinator(s) — individual(s) or institution(s) responsible for the project.
DCTERMS:CONTRIBUTOR	Participant(s) — contributors to the project beyond the main coordinator(s).
DCTERMS:INTERACTIVE RESOURCE	
DCTERMS:TITLE	Title of the interactive resource.
DCTERMS:ALTERNATIVE	Alternate name used for the resource, if applicable.
DCTERMS:DESCRIPTION	Description of the interactive resource (e.g., its purpose or audience).
DCTERMS:TYPE	Type of the interactive content (e.g., exhibition, game, visualization).
DCTERMS:CREATOR	Main person(s) or organization(s) responsible for creating the resource.
DCTERMS:CONTRIBUTOR	Additional contributors who helped in the creation.
DCTERMS:PUBLISHER	Entity that published or hosts the interactive resource.
DCTERMS:DATE	Date of creation or publication.
DCTERMS:LANGUAGE	Language(s) used in the interface or content.
DCTERMS:SUBJECT	Thematic subject(s) of the resource.
DCTERMS:SPATIAL	Spatial coverage or geographic focus of the content.
DCTERMS:TEMPORAL	Temporal coverage (historical period represented or addressed).
DCTERMS:FORMAT	File format or delivery format (e.g., HTML5, WebGL).
DCTERMS:LICENSE	Usage license for the resource (e.g., CC BY-SA, proprietary).
DCTERMS:RIGHTSHOLDER	Person or entity holding intellectual property rights.
FOAF:HOMEPAGE	Main access point or URL to the resource.
DCTERMS:ISPARTOF	Indicates whether the resource belongs to a larger project or collection.
DCTERMS:SOFTWARE	
DCTERMS:TITLE	Official name of the software tool.
DCTERMS:ALTERNATIVE	Alternative name or abbreviation used for the software.
DCTERMS:DESCRIPTION	Description of the software's functionality and scope.
DCTERMS:TYPE	Type of tool (e.g., library, application, plugin).
DCTERMS:CREATOR	Main developer(s) or institution(s) who created the software.
DCTERMS:CONTRIBUTOR	Individuals or organizations who contributed to the development.
DCTERMS:PUBLISHER	Organization or group that maintains or distributes the software.
DCTERMS:DATE	Release or publication date of the software.
DCTERMS:LANGUAGE	Programming language(s) or interface language(s).
DCTERMS:SUBJECT	Domain of application (e.g., epigraphy, GIS, 3D modeling).
DCTERMS:FORMAT	Distribution format or package type (e.g., ZIP, GitHub repo, executable).
DCTERMS:LICENSE	Usage license (e.g., MIT, GPL, proprietary).

DCTERMS:RIGHTSHOLDER	Legal holder of the intellectual property rights.
FOAF:HOME PAGE	Official website or main access point.
DCTERMS:ISPARTOF	If part of a larger software suite or infrastructure project.
DCTERMS:DATASET	
DCTERMS:TITLE	Title of the dataset.
DCTERMS:DESCRIPTION	A concise description of the dataset's content and purpose.
DCTERMS:TYPE	Type or category of dataset (e.g., point cloud, tabular, image set).
DCTERMS:CREATOR	Main author(s) or institution(s) that created the dataset.
DCTERMS:CONTRIBUTOR	Additional contributors involved in the dataset's creation.
DCTERMS:PUBLISHER	Entity responsible for publishing or hosting the dataset.
DCTERMS:DATE	Date of publication or creation of the dataset.
DCTERMS:SUBJECT	Thematic subjects covered by the dataset.
DCTERMS:SPATIAL	Geographic area(s) represented in the dataset.
DCTERMS:TEMPORAL	Time period(s) covered by the dataset.
DCTERMS:FORMAT	File format of the dataset (e.g., CSV, XML, GeoTIFF).
DCTERMS:LANGUAGE	Language(s) used in the content of the dataset.
DCTERMS:LICENSE	Usage license under which the dataset is distributed.
DCTERMS:RIGHTS	Legal holder of the intellectual property rights.
DCTERMS:ISPARTOF	If applicable, project or collection the dataset belongs to.
DCTERMS:IDENTIFIER	Persistent identifier (e.g., DOI, internal ID).
DCTERMS:SOURCE	Reference to the original source from which the dataset was derived.
DCTERMS:RELATION	Other datasets or resources related to this one.
FOAF:HOME PAGE	Main URL or access point for the dataset.